

Single Particle Strength Distributions: Heavy Tails and Extreme Values

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Strength distributions of single particles tested in diametral compression are reviewed. The particles encompass a wide range of material types—glasses, single crystals, weakly bound agglomerates of smaller substituents, and strongly bound polycrystalline aggregates—and encompass a wide range of specimen sizes—from sub-micrometer to tens of millimeters. The particles are regarded as brittle and the strengths are thus regarded as reflecting fracture controlling flaws. Attention is focused on the effects of particle size on experimental strength distributions. Major elements of the review are an extensive survey of particle strength data dating back over 50 years, presentation of strength distribution data in a uniform, unbiased format, and applications of recently developed analyses to interpret strength distributions in terms of underlying flaw populations. A major finding of the review is that most observed particle strength distributions are concave, not sigmoidal, reflecting flaw populations characterized by a “heavy tail.” The extreme value distributions generated by strength measurements on ensembles of differently sized particles are considered in some detail. In particular, the distinctions between deterministic size effects—in which different size particles systematically sample multiple flaw populations—and stochastic size effects—in which different size particles randomly sample a single flaw population—are made clear. Many of the physical phenomena described here have been obscured by the historical use of linearized coordinates reflecting a Weibull description.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Stochastic effects in mechanical behavior of small-scale components are observed in all modes of deformation, including randomness in elastic buckling of patterned dielectric lines on compressive substrates (Friedman *et al.*, 2016), variable initiation in plastic deformation of metals during blunt indentation (Morris *et al.*, 2011), and broad distributions in fracture strengths of microelectromechanical systems (MEMS) devices during tensile loading (Cook *et al.*, 2019). It is the third of these phenomena, fracture, specifically the fracture strength distributions of brittle single particles, that is the subject of this review. Small particles provide insight into the physics of fracture by enabling the possibility that each particle contains only one strength-controlling flaw and strength distributions are thus a direct measure of material flaw populations. That physics is extended by the study of larger particles that contain multiple flaws and exhibit strengths drawn from distributions reflecting stochastic and deterministic extreme value size effects. This review takes advantage of recent analyses relating strength distributions and flaw populations (Cook and DelRio, 2019ab, Cook *et al.*, 2019), and applies the analyses to an extensive survey of particle strength distributions dating back over 50 years and generated from newly-digitized measurements. Apart from providing physical insights into stochastic and extreme value phenomena, the review is made timely by presenting particle strength distributions for direct application in many areas of current interest, including minimization of energy usage in mining (crushing and transport of rock) (Tromans, 2008) and construction (storage and preparation of cement) (Schneider *et al.*, 2011); environmental remediation (stabilization of beach and river sand and pebbles) (Matthews, 1983; Novák-Szabó *et al.*, 2018); optimization of strong materials (dispersion weakening or strengthening) (Wallin, 1987; Nan and Clarke, 1996); and, even, maximizing nutrition (chewability of food) (Constantino *et al.* 2010; Lee *et al.*, 2011) . The application of particle strength measurements to advance many of these areas has historically been impeded by presentation of most data in a biased format. The review reveals many new phenomena by presenting the digitized strength distributions in an unbiased way and applying new analysis methods.

It has long been known and simply explained that there are stochastic effects in the failure of brittle components. Based on the work of Inglis (1913) considering stress concentrations at notches, Griffith (1921) used energy balance methods to show that the strengths of components

formed from brittle materials were controlled by small (sub millimeter) cracks: the larger the crack, the smaller the strength, with the exact relationship determined by the surface energy of the material and the strain energy change generated by the crack in the component. If an intended structural component contains a single crack or flaw, determination of component strength as a function of flaw geometry and residual stress state, material microstructure, component environment, and applied loading rate is now a well-understood fracture mechanics problem (Lawn, 1993). If a group of components is assembled, each containing a single, but different, flaw and the strength of each component subsequently measured, the resulting strength distribution reflects the distribution of flaw characteristics within the group, often dominated by crack length. Usually, however, each component contains a multitude of flaws, usually all different. The behavior of a component in a strength test is then still easily determined if the flaws act independently, as attention can then focus on the behavior of the largest, most potent, or strength-controlling flaw that exhibits the least resistance to failure or smallest strength. (Other, more resistant, flaws will respond to the applied stress but will not cause component failure.) If a group of such components containing multiple flaws is then assembled and tested, the resulting strength distribution reflects the distribution of the smallest, or minimally extreme, strengths in the group of components and is conjugate to the distribution of the largest, or maximally extreme, flaws. The strength distribution of a group of components, each containing multiple flaws, is then an extreme value distribution. Usually the flaws in a group of components are a subset of a much larger set constituting the entire population of flaws in the bulk material from which the test components were sampled. Soon after the work of Griffith, it was recognized by Weibull (1939) and Epstein (1948ab) that the strength distribution of a group of components containing independent flaws was an extreme value distribution determined by the material flaw population and the number of flaws in each component, and hence, by implication, the physical size of the components. The distributions described qualitatively by Weibull (1939) and quantitatively by Epstein (1948ab) thus represented a stochastic extreme value size effect.

In the intervening decades, the above contributions of Weibull and Epstein have been overshadowed by the myriad applications of the stretched exponential function popularized by Weibull (1951). The “Weibull function” provides for simple arithmetic description of distributions arising in many phenomena, including groups of component strengths, and has been incorrectly associated with size effects and flaw independence, often termed weakest link behavior, in strength

measurements The function is easily linearized, leading to a common method of transforming measured strength data for presentation, in most cases severely obscuring the underlying strength distribution and providing the completely misleading impression that the function has a physical basis. The majority, but not all, of the particle strength distribution data included in this review were published in Weibull function transformed coordinates, although other transformed coordinates were sometimes used, *e.g.*, log normal, used by the King and Tavares groups (King and Bourgeois, 1993; Tavares and King, 1998). The transformations rendered comparisons between distributions, comparisons with analyses, and assessments of stochastic or other size effects almost impossible. To enable the review and allow for direct comparisons, the data here are presented in a uniform format of an unbiased empirical distribution function (edf) of observed strengths. In all cases, the data were obtained by extensive manual digitization of published figures and post-digitization analyses, including “back” transformation, conversion from particle failure force or failure energy units, and conversion from particle mass units. In most of the particle research considered here, strength distributions were presented as the object of study and the effects of particle size were noted. In very few studies were the widths and forms of the strength distributions discussed. In no case was there quantitative analysis of the strength distributions and the underlying strength-controlling flaw populations.

Following this Introduction (section I), the review here will be divided into a further nine major sections: (II) Background, including an outline of strength measurement and commonly observed behavior, definition of the edf, and presentation of representative large specimen and particle strength edf observations, making clear that particle strength distributions are physically distinct; (III) Analysis, including definitions of the parameters required to define population and sample distributions, how, operationally, such distributions are related, and interpretation of the strength data from section II in terms of flaw populations, making clear that particle flaw populations are mathematically distinct, in being “heavy-tailed.” In addition, clear distinction is made between stochastic size effects—in which different size particles randomly sample a single flaw population and deterministic size effects—in which different size particles systematically sample multiple flaw populations. (IV) Review of small, < 1 mm diameter, particle strength behavior—these particles provide the best chance of containing a single strength-containing flaw and direct assessment of the flaw population; (V) Review of medium, between 1 mm and 10 mm diameter, particle strengths—these are the most common particles, contain a few flaws each, and often

exhibit stochastic extreme value strength effects mediated by size; (VI) Review of large, > 10 mm diameter, particle strengths—these particles contain many flaws each, usually exhibit stochastic extreme value strength effects and often exhibit superposed deterministic extreme value effects, both effects mediated by size. The distinctions in behavior in sections IV, V, and VI are not absolute and most particles in these sections are natural materials such as salt, sand, quartz, soil, coal, limestone, rocks and minerals, and railway ballast. The next section, (VII), reviews strength distributions of engineered particles, including alumina, glass, iron ore pellets, cement, catalysts, ice, and food. The final sections consider strength distributions for the total set of particles examined here, in three ways: (VIII) the overall quantitative trends; (IX) a Discussion of what has been learned, qualitatively, in terms of physical processes and previous work; and (X) a Conclusion, with suggestions for future work. In all, over 180 strength distributions including over 11 400 individual particle measurements and more than 30 materials systems, are examined.

The emphasis throughout the review is on the quantitative phenomenology of strength distributions and presentation and analysis of numerical values of strength. Many groups have published extensive measurements in this area, including: the early work of the Bradt group (1986-1988) on ceramic-related materials (Kschinka *et al.*, 1986), (Wong *et al.*, 1987), and (Bertrand *et al.*, 1988); the work of the King and Tavares groups (1993-2018) that initially established energy measurement methods, mostly applied to rocks and minerals, (King and Bourgeois, 1993), (Tavares and King, 1998), (Tavares, 1999, 2004), (Tavares and Cerqueria, 2006), (Tavares and das Neves, 2008), (Barrios *et al.*, 2011), (Ribas *et al.*, 2014), (Cavalcanti and Tavares, 2018), and (Tavares *et al.*, 2018); the McDowell group (1996-2018) that mostly performed work on soils, (McDowell *et al.*, 1996), (McDowell and Amon, 2000), (McDowell, 2001, 2002), (McDowell and Humphreys, 2002), (Lim *et al.*, 2004), (de Bono, and McDowell, 2018ab); the Salman group (2000-2005) that focused on impact velocity effects, (Salman and Gorham, 2000), (Salman *et al.*, 2002, 2003), and (Gorham and Salman, 2005); the Peukert, Tomas, and Portnikov groups (2002-2019), (Vogel and Peukert, 2002), (Antonyuk *et al.*, 2005, 2010), (Khanal *et al.*, 2008), (Aman *et al.*, 2010), (Rozenblat *et al.*, 2011), (Müller, *et al.*, 2013), (Portnikov *et al.*, 2013), (Russell *et al.*, 2014), (Portnikov and Kalman, 2014, 2018, 2019), (Paul *et al.*, 2014, 2015), (Liburkin *et al.*, 2015), and (Herre *et al.*, 2017). and the Gustafsson group (2009-2017) (Gustafsson, 2009, 2013abc, 2017). Many other aspects of particle behavior are important in interpreting such values, particularly observations of particle failure mechanisms (Shipway and Hutchings, 1993), (Tsoungui *et al.*,

1999), (Salman and Gorham, 2000), (Nakata *et al.*, 2001a), (Procopio *et al.*, 2003), (Chaudhri, 2004), (Wu *et al.*, 2004), (Gorham and Salman, 2005), (Khanal *et al.*, 2008), (Paul *et al.*, 2015), (Wang and Coop, 2016), (Norazirah *et al.*, 2016), (Satone *et al.*, 2017), (Parab *et al.*, 2017), (Gustafsson *et al.* 2017), and (Wang *et al.*, 2019), but also including characterization of particle size distributions, examination of load-displacement behavior during failure, analytical stress distribution calculations, and numerical calculations, especially discrete element modeling (DEM) and its extensions of single particle, *e.g.*, (Carmona *et al.*, 2008), (Hanley , *et al.*, 2015), (Nguyen *et al.*, 2015), and multiple particle failure, *e.g.*, (Lobo-Guerrero and Vallejo, 2006a), (de Bono and McDowell, 2018ab) and finite element modelling (Žagar *et al.*, 2018). These aspects will not be addressed in detail in this review.

II. BACKGROUND

Figure 1(a) shows a typical configuration for a single particle strength test. The particle is placed between two stiff, hard, parallel platens that are displaced towards each other, deforming and eventually breaking the particle. The platen displacement w is usually controlled by a universal mechanical testing machine that generates force L to maintain the imposed displacement and $L(w)$ is monitored as the particle is deformed. As in most contact problems, L and w are positive and compressive when directed into the contact and across the particle diameter and the configuration of Fig. 1(a) is referred to as diametral loading or diametral compression. In two dimensions (disk-like configurations) and three dimensions (sphere- or particle-like configurations), a *tensile* stress develops in the center of the component transverse to the compressively loaded diameter (uniaxial tension in two dimensions, biaxial in three). The configuration of Fig. 1(a) is thus ideal for measuring the tensile deformation and fracture properties of brittle materials without the complications of specimen gripping. Hence, the two-dimensional configuration is also known as the “Brazilian” or “indirect” tensile test, first considered in detail by Jaeger and Hoskins (1966) and Jaeger (1967) in the context of measurements of rock strength. Further details, calculations of stress fields, and reviews of two-dimensional loading behavior are provided by Darvell (1990), Procopio *et al.* (2003), and Li and Wong (2013). The three-dimensional configuration of interest here was most notably considered in the early work of Hiramatsu and Oka (1966) (HO), also in consideration of rock strength. Further details, calculations of stress fields, and reviews of three-dimensional loading behavior are given in Chau *et al.* (2000), Tsoungui *et al.* (1999), Luscher *et al.* (2007), Antonyuk *et al.* (2010), and Paul *et al.* (2014), illustrating much greater focus on small particles. The simple HO tensile stress analysis will form the basis for many of the strengths reported here.

Particle diameter is often measured prior to a strength test by first sieving a large population of particles into smaller sub-populations classified by diameter (Brecker, 1974), (Bertrand *et al.*, 1988), (Sikong *et al.*, 1990), and (Huang *et al.*, 1993). Separate samples are then taken from the sub-populations for diameter and strength measurements. The effective particle diameter in a strength test, D , is often complicated by the fact that particles frequently exhibit exterior angular facets and are not ideally spherical, and, in addition, often display exterior surface layers that are more compliant and softer than an interior core, indicative of surface asperities and surface

porosity (Vallet and Charmet, 1995), (Brzesowsky *et al.* (2011)). Sometimes this issue is overcome by taking the effective particle diameter as the instantaneous separation of the platens when the contact stiffness, dL/dw , exceeds a specified threshold during a strength test, also setting $L = 0$ and $w = 0$ at this condition (Luscher, 2007). An irregularly-shaped particle with a softer outer layer indicated by shading is illustrated in Fig. 1(a).

Figure 1(b) shows typical particle force-displacement responses, recorded during strength tests of cement clinkers of nominal diameter $D = 6$ mm by Vallet and Charmet (1995) (for brevity, here and throughout, data in Figures are identified by the first author and publication year of the source). The L - w loading responses initially exhibited some compliance, small positive dL/dw , and load drops, negative dL/dw , before exhibiting stiffer, linear, constant dL/dw , regions prior to failure of the particles at peak force, L_{peak} . The linear regions exhibited similar slopes, but the peak force values exhibited considerable variability, suggesting that the particle and contact geometries were relatively invariant just prior to failure but that the condition for instability—the particle strength and by implication, dominant flaw size—was variable. Similar variability in peak force at failure is observed in other geometries for single particle strength-testing, including concentrated loading (Hiramatsu and Oka, 1966), passing particles between rotating rollers (Brecker, 1974) and (Huang *et al.*, 1993, 1995), instrumented ball drop (King and Bourgeois, 1993), (Tavares and King, 1998), and (Tavares, 1999), impact of moving particles onto hard surfaces (Salman *et al.*, 2002, 2003), ultrasonic fragmentation (Knoop *et al.*, 2016), ballistic impact of moving surfaces onto particles (Gustafsson *et al.*, 2017), and biaxial loading (Satone *et al.*, 2017). Minor variations from the overall form of the L - w responses shown in Fig. 1(b) arise from specific test and particle configurations, including the commonly observed absence of the initial compliant region if the particles are “hard” (Kapur and Fuerstenau, 1967), (King and Bourgeois, 1993), (Antonyuk *et al.*, 2005), (Aman *et al.*, 2010), (Portnikov *et al.*, 2013), (Liburkin *et al.*, 2015), (Satone *et al.*, 2017), (Nad and Saramak, 2018), (Cavalcanti and Tavares, 2018), and (Tavares *et al.*, 2018), greater load drops if the testing system itself is compliant, (Verspui *et al.*, 1997), (Tavares and King, 1998), (Subero-Couroyer *et al.*, 2003), and (Singh *et al.*, 2016), and a small remnant supported force and small load drops after peak force, indicative of particle crushing, if platen or roller displacement is not halted by the test system (Brecker, 1974), (Huang *et al.*, 1993), (Antonyuk *et al.*, 2005), (Aman *et al.*, 2010), (Wang *et al.*, 2015), and (Wang *et al.*, 2019). Attention in this review,

however, is focused on the variability of the peak force value and the underlying distribution of particle strengths.

FIG. 1. (a) Schematic exterior diagram of single particle strength measurement using a conventional platen apparatus. The particle, size characterized by diameter D , is deformed in diametral compression between two stiff, hard platens by imposing a displacement, w , and monitoring the required force (load), L . Usually contact is set by $L = w = 0$ when dL/dw exceeds a given small value, taking into account the possibility of compliant, soft outer layers on the particle. (b) Typical force-displacement, $L-w$, responses for brittle particles tested in diametral compression, exhibiting initial erratic compliance followed by similar stiffness prior to failure at variable peak force values, L_{peak} . Responses for $D = 6$ mm cement clinkers (Vallet and Charmet, 1995).

In most of the research reviewed here, particle strength values, σ , were determined from peak force values, L_{peak} , and particle diameters, D , using the calibrated HO equation (Hiramatsu and Oka, 1966):

$$\sigma = 0.9L_{\text{peak}}/D^2. \quad (1)$$

The 0.9 coefficient was determined from calculations of the tensile stress field generated at the center of a sphere loaded in diametral compression by contact forces distributed over small surface zones. For the zones examined, the tensile stress was almost uniform, relative variation about $\pm 5\%$, in a region at the center of the sphere, about $D/2$ in size. Figure 2 is a schematic diagram of a spherical particle diametrically-loaded as in Fig. 1 (shown dashed) with the interior biaxial tensile stress field determined by Hiramatsu and Oka indicated (arrows). The 0.9 coefficient was verified by comparative strength measurements on irregularly shaped test pieces and discs of several rocks, showing relative agreement to within about $\pm 10\%$ (Hiramatsu and Oka, 1966). The validity of Eq. (1), was further investigated by Luscher *et al.* (2007) in strength tests of an extensive set of kaolinite and bauxite aggregates using internally consistent measurements of particle diameter (see above), peak load, and contact area, and showed that although the HO equation underestimated the internally-consistent strength calculation by a relative factor of about 5%, the relative experimental strength uncertainty varied from 4% to 9% at the 90% confidence level. Luscher *et al.* concluded, in agreement with other investigators, that the factor 0.9 in the HO equation was valid for determining the tensile strength of particles and the HO equation will be used here throughout.

In some reported works, the failure characteristics of the particles were reported as L_{peak} vs D , *e.g.*, (Capes, 1971), such that strength σ could be evaluated directly from Eq. (1). In some works, failure characteristics were reported as L_{peak} vs M , *e.g.*, (Kapur and Fuerstenau, 1967), where M is the mass of the particle. In those cases, the diameter of the particle was first calculated from $D = (6M/\pi\rho)^{1/3}$, where ρ is the effective density of the particle (taking porosity into account). In some works, failure characteristics were reported as E_m , *e.g.*, (Tavares and King., 1998), where E_m is the specific energy (energy/mass) required for particle failure. It is recognized that $E_m = U_E/\rho$, where U_E is the strain energy density (energy/volume) at failure, expressed in terms of particle strength as $U_E = \sigma^2/2Y$ for linear elastic loading, where Y is a characteristic elastic modulus related to the particle stiffness. In this case, the relationship between strength and specific energy is given by

$\sigma = (2Y\rho)^{1/2} E_m^{1/2}$. The many observations of near linear loading to failure (*i.e.*, the absence of compliance changes on loading, see above) suggest that the relationship $\sigma \sim E_m^{1/2}$ should describe particle failure. Direct observations (Tavares and King, 1998), (Ryu and Saito, 1991) show the relationship to be obeyed and hence was used here; for the materials examined the coefficient $(2Y\rho)^{1/2} = 1.5 \text{ MPa (J/kg)}^{-1/2}$ with about $\pm 10 \%$ variability. (Similarly, it is recognized that in a free particle impact test, *e.g.*, Salman *et al.*, (2002, 2003), that $E_m \sim v^2$, where v is the particle velocity prior to impact, and thus $\sigma \sim v$. The uncertainty in calibration precluded analysis by this method here.)

FIG. 2. Schematic interior diagram of single particle strength measurement by the “indirect” tensile test. The particle is loaded in diametral compression via platens, indicated by dashed lines. For the spherical particle indicated, a near uniform biaxial tensile stress, σ , indicated by arrows, is generated transverse to the compressive axis in the center of the particle.

Figure 3 is a set of plots of particle strength, σ , as a function of particle diameter, D , with data derived from the works of Kapur and Furstenau (1967), Capes, (1971), Vallet and Charmet (1995), Wang *et al.* 2019), Nakata *et al.* (2001b), and Sikong *et al.* (1990) (here and throughout, the total number of individual particle strength measurements, N_{tot} , derived from a published work and used here in analyses is provided in the figure caption). The plots are drawn to the same scale (100×30) in logarithmic coordinates and exemplify many of the aspects of particle strength observations reviewed here. The Figure includes a diversity of particle types and sizes, from porous aggregates of smaller constituents probably predominantly bound by hydrogen and van der Waals bonds, the limestone pellets, sand agglomerates, and cement clinkers of Figs. 3(a), (b), and (c), to dense, single-phase particles of coal, sand, and minerals, Figs. 3(d), (e), and (f), respectively. The collection includes a range of sizes from approximately 20 mm, Fig. 3(a) to 2 nm, Fig. 3(f) and a typical individual particle study extended over about a factor of 10 in particle diameter. The collection of particle types exhibited strengths ranging from less than 0.1 MPa, Fig. 3(a), to nearly 1 GPa, Fig. 3(f) and a typical individual particle study exhibited about a factor of 10 in strength range. The predominant characteristic of Fig. 3 is that all particle types exhibited decreases in strength with particle diameter; the solid lines are guides to the eye of slopes -0.5 and -1.0 , encompassing the trends. Previous decreasing trends in strength with particle diameter for these and other observations have been characterized by empirical power-law slopes, including -0.35 ± 0.2 (Kapur and Furstenau, 1967), -0.4 ± 0.3 (Capes, 1971), -0.5 ± 0.4 (Vallet and Charmet, 1995), -0.34 to -0.42 , as cited by McDowell and Amon (2000), -0.79 ± 0.3 (Nakata *et al.*, 2001b), -0.75 , as cited by Nakata *et al.* (2001b), -0.7 ± 0.5 and -1.1 ± 0.2 (Lobo-Guerrero *et al.*, 2006b), -0.52 ± 0.25 (Wang *et al.*, 2015), and -0.42 ± 0.3 (Xu *et al.*, 2016), where the uncertainties are estimated from the published data. The trend extends out to very large sizes, as slopes of -0.26 to -0.43 were determined for 3 mm to 1600 mm “particles” of coal (Moomivand, 1999). As will be seen, the negative values and large relative uncertainties well describe particle behavior but are probably not estimates of a universal dependence.

FIG. 3. Logarithmic plots of strength σ vs diameter D for six particle systems, showing measurements for individual particles, illustrating decreasing strength trends and dispersions. (a) Limestone pellets, number of specimens, $N_{\text{tot}} = 62$ (Kapur and Furstenau, 1967). (b) Sand agglomerates, $N_{\text{tot}} = 67$ Capes, (1971). (c) Cement clinkers, $N_{\text{tot}} = 309$ (Vallet and Charmet, 1995). (d) Coal, $N_{\text{tot}} = 145$ (Wang *et al.* 2019). (e) Sand grains, $N_{\text{tot}} = 368$ (Nakata *et al.*, 2001b). (f) Mineral grains, $N_{\text{tot}} = 8$ (Sikong *et al.* (1990).

The second clear characteristic of Fig. 3 is that the strength measurements exhibit considerable dispersion or variation; for a selected particle diameter, the observed strengths can exhibit a factor of 10 range from the smallest to the largest. This behavior is well illustrated in the observations of Fig. 3(e), in which the sand particles were sorted into groups of similar diameters prior to strength testing and each group exhibited a range of 10 in strengths. This last point highlights a final observation from Fig. 3. The relative strength dispersion was invariant with diameter for all particles implying that the absolute strength dispersion decreased with increasing diameter. An alternative description, summarizing the above, is that although there are clear material dependences, large particle strengths are weaker than small particle strengths and large particle strength distributions appear narrower than small particle distributions. Representative particle diameters are a few millimeters and representative particle strengths are a few tens of megapascals. The central questions suggested by Fig. 3 to be addressed in this review are then: what is the strength distribution for a given particle diameter? And, how does the particle strength distribution depend on diameter and material?

The predominant vehicle used for presentation and comparison of strength measurements of groups of components is the empirical distribution function, the edf. The components may be “large” specimens with strengths given by appropriate bending, tension, or compression formulae or “small” particles with strengths given by the HO formula of Eq. (1) or similar. The development of the edf closely follows that recently described for MEMS devices, ceramic strengths, and indentation crack lengths. (Cook and DeIRio, 2019ab, Cook *et al.*, 2019, Cook, 2020) A group consists of N components, with individual component strengths σ_i indexed by i from 1 to N . The strengths are ranked such that the smallest and largest values of σ_i correspond to $i = 1$ and $i = N$, respectively, and the conjugate quantity $Pr(i) = (i - 0.5)/N$ is assigned to each value. The discrete function $[\sigma_i, Pr(i)]$ is then the edf, notated here as $Pr(\sigma)$. $Pr(\sigma)$ extends over the domain σ_1 to σ_N and range of ≈ 0 to ≈ 1 . $Pr(\sigma)$ is the probability that a randomly selected member of the set i has a strength less than σ_i . Supplies and costs of particles are usually not an impediment to single particle mechanical testing, and the testing itself is conceptually simple, Figs. 1(a) and 2. Although handling of millimeter or smaller scale particles can be difficult and instrumentation of tests at small loads (few Newtons) and displacements (sub-millimeter) can also be difficult, the first point has led to many studies composed of statistically viable numbers of particle measurements, i.e., N is great enough so that edf variations can be assessed. Assessment begins here with a brief

description of the behavior of large specimens, thereby providing reference points for examination of particles.

Figure 4 shows strength edf plots, $Pr(\sigma)$ vs σ , constructed as described from the works of Phani and De (1987), de Wit *et al.* (2017), Easler *et al.* (1982), and Cook and DeRio (2019b) for four different materials tested in bending, the most common testing geometry for brittle ceramics and glasses. The specimen sizes were all of order several millimeters and N ranged from 49 to 103 (here and throughout, details of specimen sizes and N are provided in the figure caption; note that N_{tot} and N are often different). To assess and compare $Pr(\sigma)$ for each material easily and clearly the plots are provided in an unbiased format, to be used throughout: The data are presented in linear coordinates, the abscissa extends from 0 to approximately the maximum observed strength, σ_N , and the ordinate extends from 0 to 1.1. Although the magnitudes of the strength domains, σ_1 to σ_N , differ, there are clear similarities in the edf behavior of the four sets of bending tests: the domain in each case extends to the maximum strength from a minimum of about half that value, *i.e.*, the σ_N/σ_1 strength ratio is about 2, and the data in each case exhibit sigmoidal behavior, indicated by the best-fit lines, described below. Although data as extensive as those shown in Fig. 4 are not common, the observations are typical of brittle beams tested in bending. Figure 5 shows similar strength edf plots constructed from the work of Gaither *et al.* (2013), Meininger *et al.* (2016), Kotchick *et al.* (1975), and Al-Manaseer *et al.* (2011) for four different materials tested in tension or compression. Here, the specimen sizes varied considerably from tens of micrometers to hundreds of millimeters, N ranged from 31 to 1025, and the plotting scheme of Fig. 4 was used. Although here the strength domains differed substantially, there are clear similarities in the edf behavior of these four materials, bars and fibers in tension and columns in compression, with each other and with the bending data of Fig. 4: the σ_N/σ_1 strength ratio was about 2 and the data exhibited sigmoidal behavior. Also, once again, although data as extensive as those shown in Fig. 5 are not common, the observations are typical of brittle materials tested in tension or compression.

FIG. 4. Empirical distribution function (edf) plots of strength measurements, $Pr(\sigma)$ vs σ , for four brittle materials tested in small-scale bending. (a) Glass rods, 90 mm long \times 4 mm diameter, number of specimens, $N = 80$ (Phani and De, 1987). (b) Porous alumina tubular beams, 40 mm long \times 1.5 mm diameter, $N = 103$ (de Wit *et al.*, 2017). (c) Silicon nitride beams, 30 mm long \times 2.5 mm \times 2.5 mm, $N = 49$ (Easler *et al.* (1982)). (d) Alumina beams, 32 mm long \times 8 mm \times 0.65 mm, $N = 100$ (Cook and DeIRio, 2019b).

FIG. 5. Empirical distribution function (edf) plots of strength measurements, $Pr(\sigma)$ vs σ , for four brittle materials tested in small-scale tension or compression. (a) Silicon MEMS tensile bars, $300 \mu\text{m} \text{ long} \times 25 \mu\text{m} \times 8 \mu\text{m}$, number of specimens, $N = 209$ (Gaither *et al.*, 2013), and (b) Phosphate biomaterial compression discs, $12 \text{ mm tall} \times 6 \text{ mm} \times 6 \text{ mm}$, $N = 31$ (Meininger *et al.*, 2016). (c) Sapphire tensile filaments, $75 \text{ mm long} \times 0.25 \text{ mm diameter}$, $N = 61$ (Kotchick *et al.*, 1975). (d) Concrete compression columns, $200 \text{ mm or } 300 \text{ mm tall} \times 100 \text{ mm or } 150 \text{ mm diameter}$, $N = 1025$ (Al-Manaseer *et al.*, 2011). Note that stress axes differ in scale top to bottom.

FIG. 6. Empirical distribution function (edf) plots of strength measurements, $Pr(\sigma)$ vs σ , for four particle systems tested in diametral compression, (a) Salt particles, particle size, $D = (2.36 \text{ to } 3.35) \text{ mm}$, number of specimens, $N = 80$ (Rozenblat *et al.*, 2011). (b) Brazilian quarry rock particles, $D = (4.75 \text{ to } 5.6) \text{ mm}$, $N = 57$ (Tavares and das Neves, 2008). (c) Bauxite proppant particles, $D = (1.60 \pm 0.03) \text{ mm}$, $N = 51$ (Wong *et al.*, 1987). (d) Corundum abrasive particles, $D = 1.29$ (estimated ± 0.15) mm, $N = 73$ (Huang *et al.*, 1995).

In contrast, Fig. 6 shows strength edf plots completely different from those of Figs. 4 and 5, constructed for particles tested in diametral compression. The data are from the works of Rozenblat *et al.* (2011), Tavares and das Neves (2008), Wong *et al.* (1987), and Huang *et al.* (1995) for four different materials and particle sizes, all of order a few millimeters. N varied from 51 to 80 and the plotting scheme of Figs. 4 and 5 is used (here and throughout, published details of particle size are provided in the figure caption). Although the strength domains differ substantially, there are clear similarities in the edf behavior of the four particle systems in Fig. 6. The results exemplify those in the review: The maximum/minimum ratio in the strength domain was large, the σ_N/σ_1 strength ratio was greater than a factor of 4. The data exhibited concave responses based on steep, near-linear, behavior adjacent to the minimum strengths and shallow, extended tail, behavior adjacent to the maximum strengths. The data are not sigmoidal or even approximately symmetrical and adjacent to the minimum strengths are typified by non-zero derivatives, although there is evidence of a diminished derivative region in some cases. The concave behavior indicated by the best-fit lines is described below.

Comparison of Figs. 4, 5, and 6 makes clear that the strength distributions of large specimens and particles are different. The first are restricted and sigmoidal and the second are extended and concave. The underlying strength-controlling flaw size distributions must therefore also be different. The different spatial arrangement of applied stress in the two test geometries leads to two forms of strength-controlling flaw distributions. Large specimens are “large” in the sense that major fractions of the specimen experience the maximum applied stress during a strength test, *e.g.*, uniform tension or compression in a fiber or column, uniform moment in a symmetric beam. Particles are “small” as only a minor fraction of the specimen experiences the maximum stress in a strength test, *e.g.*, biaxial tension near the center of a particle causing brittle fracture in diametral compression. Hence, failure in strength tests on large specimens usually occurs from a wide range of spatial locations on the specimen: Failure occurs at the *extreme* flaw exhibiting the weakest strength, *independent of the flaw location*. In contrast, reciprocally, failure in strength tests on small particles usually occurs within a localized region, *e.g.*, near the particle center: Failure occurs at the maximum stress location, *independent of the flaw size*. Hence, also reciprocally, large specimens sample a small proportion of the flaw population and small particles sample a large proportion of the flaw population.

Similar reciprocity was recently demonstrated in quantitative detail in a study of notched and tensile MEMS specimens (Cook *et al.*, 2019). In this study, notches in some specimens defined the failure location and led to sampling of almost the complete flaw population and a broad strength distribution. Failure location was not defined for the tensile specimens, which in strength tests therefore represented a smaller proportion of the flaw population through stochastic extreme value size effects, leading to narrow strength distributions. The strength distributions of the large specimens and particles shown in Figs. 4, 5, and 6 are consistent with the argument in the previous paragraph and the observations of the MEMS study. This review will show that the strength distributions of most groups of particles, spanning a wide array of particle materials and sizes, resemble Fig. 6 and therefore sample a large fraction of the flaw population. The review will also show that characteristics of Figs. 4 and 5 can be present in particle strength distributions and that many systems of particles can exhibit stochastic extreme value size effects leading to narrower strength distributions as particle size increases. However, many systems of particles will also be shown to exhibit *deterministic* extreme value size effects leading to narrower *and shifted* strength distributions as particle size increases, independent of the exact form of the distribution. The next section provides the analysis to interpret the $Pr(\sigma)$ data of Figs. 4, 5, and 6, including the best-fit lines, to deconvolute strength data to obtain flaw-size distributions, to distinguish between large specimen and particle behavior, and to specify the quantitative difference between stochastic and deterministic extreme value size effects.

III. ANALYSIS

The analytical framework reviewed here closely follows that recently developed and applied in strength studies of micro-scale silicon (Si) MEMS components containing nano-scale flaws (Cook and DelRio, 2019a, Cook *et al.*, 2019). and in strength and fracture studies of meso-scale ceramic components containing micro-scale flaws (Cook and DelRio, 2019b, Cook, 2020). The framework enables analysis in two directions: In forward analysis, suited to theoretical considerations, the material flaw population is assumed *a priori*, and strength distributions are predicted based on component size and sample size, reflecting components formed from the material and sampled in groups. In reverse analysis, the practical focus of this review, strength distributions of components (here particles) are specified by experimental measurement and the underlying material flaw populations are determined based on deconvolution techniques. The framework is developed most intuitively by forward analysis beginning with an assumed flaw population. Reverse analyses are then simply implemented by performing the developed steps in reverse; additional steps required in application of the framework to experimental data are identified easily. This forward then reverse sequence is the approach used here.

A. Strength distribution prediction

A large body of material, volume Ω , constituting in this case a very large number of particles or proto-particles, many more than are to be mechanically tested, *e.g.*, a sandy beach, a container ship filled with ore pellets, a monolithic mountain of rock, can be characterized by two flaw population attributes. These attributes characterize the spatial distribution of flaws in the material and the size distribution of these flaws. The spatial distribution of flaws is most easily specified by the flaw volume density, λ , the number of flaws/volume averaged over Ω ; the total population of flaws in the material is then $\Omega\lambda$. The reciprocal $1/\lambda = \Delta V$, is the average volume occupied by a single flaw and is thus termed a fundamental volume element. The volume of a single particle is V and thus the size of a particle in terms of fundamental volume elements is $k = V/\Delta V$. Note that k need not be an integer as ΔV is defined as an average over the body of material. For ease of illustration, the development here is framed in terms of particle size and flaw density using volume, $V \sim D^3$, and flaws/volume, λ . With no change in analysis, particle size could also be specified using

surface or cross-sectional area, $A \sim D^2$, and flaw density as flaws/area, λD , or circumference or diameter, $L \sim D$, and flaw density as flaws/length, λD^2 (Cook and DelRio, 2019b).

Independent of flaw density descriptions, the material features representing the strength-controlling flaws may also vary in physical dimensionality, including volume-based pores, area-based delaminations, length-based cracks, or even dimensionless aspect ratios or coefficients (Cook and DelRio, 2019b). Here, flaw size will be taken as a crack length, c . The crack length is different for each fundamental element and locally determines the strength, such that the strength of each fundamental element is σ . If the population, $\Omega\lambda$, of elements and thus flaws is large, the crack lengths may be treated as a continuum with continuous probability density function (pdf), $f(c)$, describing crack lengths over the region of support or domain of f , $c_{\min} \leq c \leq c_{\max}$, where c_{\min} and c_{\max} are the minimum and maximum crack lengths, respectively. $f(c)$ and λ can be considered the fundamental attributes of the population. Important physical considerations are that the maximum crack length must be bounded by the finite energy used to form the particle or flaw and, analytically, must be smaller than the particle size, $c_{\max} < D$ (otherwise the particle is already broken), and the minimum crack length must be non-zero, $c_{\min} > 0$ (otherwise the crack is not strength-controlling). The continuous cumulative distribution function (cdf) of the population, $F(c)$, is given by integration of the pdf,

$$F(c) = \int_0^c f(u)du, \quad (2)$$

where u is a dummy crack length variable. $F(c)$ gives the proportion of elements in the population with cracks smaller than c and is the probability that an element selected at random will contain a crack of length smaller than c . Normalization of the pdf requires

$$\int_{c_{\min}}^{c_{\max}} f(u)du = 1, \quad (3)$$

such that the range of $F(c)$ is 0 to 1 over the domain $c_{\min} \leq c \leq c_{\max}$. More usefully here the pdf is expressed as the derivative of the cdf:

$$f(c) = dF(c)/dc. \quad (4)$$

such that $f(c)$ can be estimated from $F(c)$ and this is a major focus and methodology employed in this review. Eqs. (2) and (4) make clear that $F(c)$ is equally fundamental as $f(c)$.

The determination of $F(c)$ is usually performed by analysis of strength measurements, requiring a relationship between element strength and crack length. Here the relationship is taken as the Griffith equation (Lawn, 1993):

$$\sigma = Bc^{-1/2}, \quad (5)$$

where B is a constant with dimensions of [strength][length]^{1/2} involving the element toughness, set by the material, and the crack geometry and pre-existing stress state, set by the particle and crack formation processes. A typical value for inorganic particles is $B = 1 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$, such that a crack length of $c = 0.1 \text{ mm}$ corresponds to a strength of $\sigma = 100 \text{ MPa}$ (Lawn, 1993). Once the relationship of Eq. (5) is specified, the population of element strengths can also be specified by fundamental pdf and cdf variations, $f(\sigma)$ and $F(\sigma)$, conjugate to $f(c)$ and $F(c)$, respectively. The domain or region of support for $f(\sigma)$ and $F(\sigma)$ is conjugate to the crack length domain and bounded by σ_u and σ_{th} :

$$\sigma_u = Bc_{\min}^{-1/2}, \quad (6a)$$

where the upper bound to the element strengths, σ_u , corresponds to the minimum in crack length;

$$\sigma_{th} = Bc_{\max}^{-1/2}, \quad (6b)$$

where the lower bound, σ_{th} , corresponds to the maximum in crack length. The lower bound to the strength, σ_{th} , is known as the “threshold” strength and is critical in engineering design of mechanical loading safety factors. $f(\sigma)$ is defined in relation to $F(\sigma)$ similar to Eqs. (2)-(4) above and normalization requires the range of $F(\sigma)$ to be 0 to 1 over the domain $\sigma_{th} \leq \sigma \leq \sigma_u$. The cdf $F(\sigma)$ gives the proportion of elements in the population with strengths less than σ and is the probability that an element selected at random will exhibit a strength less than σ .

The inverse relationship between strength and crack length, Eq. (5), makes it useful to define the *complementary* cumulative distribution function (ccdf) for strength, $\bar{F}(\sigma)$, by

$$\bar{F}(\sigma) = 1 - F(\sigma). \quad (7)$$

$\bar{F}(\sigma)$ gives the proportion of elements in the population with strengths greater than σ and is thus the probability that a randomly selected element will exhibit a strength greater than σ . The domain and range of $\bar{F}(\sigma)$ are identical to those of $F(\sigma)$. The power of the cdf $\bar{F}(\sigma)$ is that on substitution of c for σ using Eq. (5), noting that large strengths imply small flaws and vice versa, the relationship between cdf responses for crack length and strength is

$$\bar{F}(\sigma) = F(c), \quad (8)$$

enabling determination of population strength cdf $\bar{F}(\sigma)$ and thus, more importantly, the population strength cdf $F(\sigma)$, to be determined from the population crack length pdf $f(c)$.

Figure 7 shows examples of five representative crack populations characterized by different $f(c)$ pdf variations. All populations have domains extending from $c_{\min} = 0.1$ mm to $c_{\max} = 1.6$ mm and $f(c)$ has been scaled by the maximum value in each case, $f(c)_{\max}$, such that all ranges are 0 to 1. The populations include Fig. 7(a), uniform; Fig 7(c), symmetric triangular; Fig. 7(e), symmetric bell-shaped; Fig. 7(g), asymmetric light (or long) tailed; and Fig. 7(i), asymmetric heavy tailed. The five conjugate strength populations characterized by $F(\sigma)$, determined as described above using $B = 1$ MPa m^{1/2}, are shown to the right of each crack population, *e.g.*, (a) \mapsto (b), *etc.* All strength populations have domains extending from $\sigma_{\text{th}} = 25$ MPa to $\sigma_{\text{u}} = 100$ MPa, a relative contraction from the crack length domain arising from Eq. (5). There are many points to note regarding Fig. 7: A first point is that symmetric pdf crack populations give rise to asymmetric cdf strength populations and vice versa. A second point is that in only one case was a clearly sigmoidal cdf observed, *e.g.*, Fig. 7(h); most strength population cdf variations were concave, consisting of a predominantly curved response, *e.g.*, Fig. 7(b), or, more often, a predominantly straight or linear response perturbed by a curved tail, *e.g.*, Fig. 7(j). A third point, by implication, is that the sigmoidal edf large specimen responses shown in Figs. 4 and 5 reflect long-tailed flaw populations, that the concave edf particle responses in Fig. 6 reflect heavy-tailed flaw populations, and that the tendency to linearity at small strengths observed in both sets of responses reflects characteristics of the substantial population densities at large flaws. Figure 7 is the basis for much of the

interpretation of strength data in this review and the points above should make clear that the features arising in strength distributions from underlying flaw populations are not always intuitive.

FIG. 7. Crack length probability density function, pdf, plots, $f(c)$, for some common flaw populations, left column: (a) Uniform; (c) Triangular; (e) Bell-shaped; (g) Long-tailed; and (i) Heavy-tailed. Strength cumulative distribution function, cdf, plots, $F(\sigma)$, conjugate to the flaw populations, right column: (b) is conjugate to (a), and so on. The heavy-tailed (i)- perturbed linear (j) combination is most prevalent for particles.

The next step in the forward analysis is to determine the *group* strength cdf, $H(\sigma)$, for similarly formed and similarly sized components sampled from the population of elements. The proportion of components in a group exhibiting strengths less than σ is $H(\sigma)$. The complementary proportion, the ccdf for the group strength, exhibiting strengths greater than σ is defined as before, $\bar{H}(\sigma) = 1 - H(\sigma)$. A component consists of k fundamental volume elements, such that a component has volume $V = k\Delta V$ and contains k cracks, each exhibiting a strength sampled from the material population according to probability $F(\sigma)$ (usually, $k \ll \Omega\lambda$). Although, for big-enough components, non-destructive evaluation (NDE) techniques can often determine the ensemble of such crack sizes within a component, only the largest or most *extreme* crack in a component is sensed by strength measurement. The element containing the largest crack exhibits the smallest strength and hence determines the measured failure strength of the component, as all other elements exhibit greater strengths (and are not sensed in the measurement). Hence, $H(\sigma)$ for a group of components is always an extreme value distribution, and, usually, $k > 1$ such that $H(\sigma) > F(\sigma)$.

$H(\sigma)$ is determined by the form and functional dependence of the population strength cdf, $F(\sigma)$, and the size of the components in terms of the number of included flaws, k . Considerable progress and utility is gained by assuming that the fundamental volume elements and thus included flaws are independent, or, equivalently, mathematically, that $F(\sigma)$ is invariant with respect to k . The probability that a single element exhibits a strength greater than σ is $\bar{F}(\sigma)$. If the k elements comprising a component are independent, the combined probability that *all* k elements will exhibit strengths greater than σ is given, multiplicatively, by $\bar{H}(\sigma) = \bar{F}(\sigma)^k$. If a group of components, all size k , is assembled, the required result is thus

$$H(\sigma) = 1 - [1 - F(\sigma)]^k. \quad (9)$$

Eq. (9) reflects the forward analysis sequence of Eqs. (2), (7), and (8), and provides a limiting continuous response for $H(\sigma)$ assuming the number of components, N , is large, such that the region of support for $H(\sigma)$ is the same as that of $F(\sigma)$. [In the domain limit of $\sigma \rightarrow \sigma_{th}$, such that $F(\sigma) \rightarrow 0$, the behavior of Eq. (9) is $H(\sigma) \approx 1 - \exp[-kF(\sigma)]$, an asymptotic result often cited in considerations of extreme value behavior for $k \gg 1$, [Epstein \(1948b\)](#), [Chao and Shetty \(1992\)](#),

Todinov (2010), Zok (2017), and Cook and DelRio (2019a). Eq. (9) provides several insights. First, and a major motivation for this review, as $k \rightarrow 1$, $H(\sigma) \rightarrow F(\sigma)$, thus capturing the possibility that small particles containing one or a few flaws can provide direct measures of material flaw populations. Second, Eq. (9) enables a clear prediction for the relation between strength distributions of different sized components containing flaws from the same population. For two such components, characterized by k_1 and k_2 , the group strength distributions are

$$H_1(\sigma) = 1 - [1 - F(\sigma)]^{k_1} \quad (10a)$$

and

$$H_2(\sigma) = 1 - [1 - F(\sigma)]^{k_2}. \quad (10b)$$

Eliminating $F(\sigma)$ between these equations gives

$$H_2(\sigma) = 1 - [1 - H_1(\sigma)]^{k_2/k_1}, \quad (11)$$

noting that the exponent k_2/k_1 is the ratio of the numbers of flaws in the different sized components. Eq. (11) shows that the strength distributions of such components, containing independent flaws drawn from the same population, are related by this ratio. A similar result was noted earlier by Shih (1980) in an extensive analytical work considering failure probability and by Wong *et al.* (1987) for an assumed volume distribution of flaws.

Although explicit absolute information (distribution, density) regarding the flaw population is lost, systems that obey Eq. (11) imply the existence of a single underlying population of independent strength-controlling flaws. Component size thence influences a group strength distribution only through the probability that a component contains an element exhibiting an extreme strength, selected from the invariant population, Eq. (9). Systems with this strength behavior will thus be referred to as exhibiting a stochastic extreme value size effect. Conversely, systems that do not obey Eq. (11) imply that a single underlying population of independent strength-controlling flaws does not exist. Physically, the implementation of different fabrication and flaw generation methods for components of different size, *e.g.*, different heat treatments or sieving techniques, or interaction between fundamental volume elements so as to remove flaw independence, *e.g.*, by coalescence or shielding, lead to the same mathematical modification of

Eq. (9): A size dependence is incorporated into the strength cdf such that $F = F(\sigma, k)$ and the simple multiplicative use of k indicative of independence is removed. In this case, the strength distribution of a group is determined by component size through *both* the population of strengths and the probability that a component contains a particular extreme strength from the population. Systems with this strength behavior will thus be referred to as exhibiting a deterministic extreme value size effect. A third insight of Eq. (9) is then the clear distinction between stochastic and deterministic size effects.

The final step in forward analysis is to predict empirical $Pr(\sigma)$ for components in a group of sample size N using $H(\sigma)$ as a basis and including experimental variability in strength measurements. **Figure 8** shows as the lower fine lines the $F(\sigma)$ strength response of a heavy-tailed population similar to Fig. 7(j). In Fig. 8(a), the upper, bold lines indicate the $H(\sigma)$ variations determined using this $F(\sigma)$ response and components of different sizes, $k = 2, 4, 8,$ and 80 , assuming a stochastic size effect and Eq. (9). As discussed, $H(\sigma) > F(\sigma)$, moving further from the population response as k increases until, for large components, most strengths are close to the threshold. Fig. 8(b) repeats these $H(\sigma)$ variations as shaded lines. The different symbols in Fig. 8(b) indicate simulated $Pr(\sigma)$ responses for the different component sizes using a common sample size of $N = 100$. Discrete strengths were selected stochastically using the underlying $H(\sigma)$ probabilities. The strengths were then modified using a multiplicative noise factor representing experimental strength measurement variability of $\pm 5\%$. Finally, the ranking procedure described in the previous section was implemented to generate the symbols in Fig. 8(b). A key point of Fig. 8(b) is that the simulated data for $k = 2$ closely resemble qualitatively and quantitatively the observations of Fig. 6, suggesting the selected heavy-tailed population and measurement parameters are appropriate experimental descriptions of particle failure. An additional experimental consideration is that, for all k values, the largest values of the discrete strength data lie well below the upper bound (100 MPa) of the underlying population. Fig. 8(b) reinforces the conclusion above that strength distributions of components related by stochastic size effects extend over the same strength domain and, in particular, appear as “fanned out” responses originating at the threshold. The absolute strength distribution *contractions* noted in Fig. 2 are consistent with the stochastic fanning out in Fig. 8, but the strength distribution *shifts* also noted, indicative of deterministic size effects, are absent in Fig. 8.

FIG. 8. Plots illustrating stochastic size effects on the strength distributions of particles from extreme value analysis. (a) Continuous cumulative strength distribution responses, $H(\sigma)$, for particles of increasing size, $k = 2, 4, 8,$ and 80 (bold lines). (b) Discrete empirical distribution, edf, $Pr(\sigma)$, responses simulated for samples of 100 particles at the sizes indicated by gray lines from (a), *cf* Fig. 6. The base population response equivalent to $k = 1, F(\sigma)$, is shown as a grayed line in both cases.

Qualitative depictions of the above analyses are summarized in schematic diagrams of example test systems in **Figs. 9 and 10**. Figure 9 illustrates the difference between large specimens and particles and the potential of particles to provide a direct measure of flaw populations by avoiding extreme value effects. Figure 9(a) is a schematic diagram of a group of $N=5$ tensile specimens. The loading leading to tensile stress is indicated by arrows on one specimen. The specimens are of uniform size and each consists of 10 fundamental volume elements, $V = 10\Delta V$. Each fundamental volume element contains (by definition) one flaw, although not all flaws are the same size (for illustration, orientations shown also differ). The specimens are regarded as “large,” as every volume element experiences maximum, uniform, stress, such that $k = 10$. On loading, the entire ensemble of flaws within a specimen also experiences maximum stress, shown as bold. Failure ensues from the largest, extreme flaw within the ensemble, independent of location within the specimen, shown shaded. The distribution of strengths for the group reflects the extreme value distribution of flaws. The majority of flaws within the ensembles and the overall population of flaws are not sensed by strength measurements, which are biased by extreme value effects towards the small strength threshold.

Figure 9(b) is a schematic diagram of a group of $N=5$ particle specimens. The loading leading to tensile stress at the center of the particle is indicated by arrows on one specimen. The specimens are of uniform size and here each consists of 9 fundamental volume elements, $V = 9\Delta V$. The specimens are regarded as “small,” as very few volume elements experience maximum stress, such that here $k = 1$. On loading, the central flaw, shown as bold, experiences significantly greater tension than all others in the ensemble, shown as dotted. Failure ensues from the flaw at the central location, independent of size, shown shaded. The distribution of strengths for the group of particles reflects the population of flaws and extreme value effects are avoided in strength measurements.

FIG. 9. Schematic diagrams illustrating the differences in (a) extreme value effects in strengths of large tensile specimens and (b) direct assessment of flaw population in strengths of small particles. In (a), failure occurs at the largest flaw, independent of location. In (b), failure occurs at the center location, independent of flaw size.

Figure 10 illustrates the difference between stochastic and deterministic size effects for particles. To the left in Fig. 10 is a schematic diagram of a particle from Fig. 9, for which $V = 9\Delta V$ and $k = 1$. Figure 10(a) is a schematic diagram of another, larger particle for which the flaw population—flaw size distribution, $f(c)$, flaw density, $(1/\Delta V)$ —is invariant with the first particle and the only alteration is particle size, such that $V = 36\Delta V$. As in Fig. 9, the particle is regarded as small when examined in a strength test, such that on diametral loading only the center of particle experiences significant tension. In this case, however, as the particle is larger, the ensemble of stressed flaws, shown bold, is larger and $k = 4$ (other flaws are shown dotted). Failure ensues from the largest flaw, shown shaded, from within the significantly stressed ensemble. Limited extreme value effects thus apply (there may be larger flaws within the particle) as particle size influences the number of flaws assessed in a strength test, as in Fig. 9(a). This is a stochastic size effect as only the probability of a given flaw alters with particle size.

Figure 10(b) is a schematic diagram of an alternative larger particle in which the flaw population is altered from that of the small particle. The flaw population has been changed by the inclusion of some larger flaws (c_{\max} is larger) and the flaw density has decreased (ΔV is larger). As previously, the particle is still regarded as small when examined in a strength test, such that on diametral loading only the center of particle experiences significant tension. In this case, however, as the fundamental volume is larger, the number of stressed flaws, shown bold, is reduced and $k = 1$ (other flaws are shown dotted). Failure ensues from the flaw at the central location, shown shaded, independent of size. Extreme value effects are thus obviated as in Fig. 9(b). This is a deterministic size effect as the flaw population is determined by particle size.

The following section describes the analysis required to determine a quantitative description of the particle systems of Fig. 10.

(a) Stochastic Size Effect

(b) Deterministic Size Effect

FIG. 10. Schematic diagram illustrating the difference in (a) stochastic size effects and (b) deterministic size effects as particle size increases from left to right. In (a), the flaw population is invariant and particle size dictates flaw probability. In (b) particle size determines the flaw population and probability effects are minimized.

B. Flaw population determination

A population of material volume elements is sampled to form components that exhibit discrete strength values, σ_i , that are the basis for the generation of the discrete edf $Pr(\sigma)$. $Pr(\sigma)$ is a statistical estimator of the continuous extreme value function $H(\sigma)$, the limiting strength distribution for components of size k within large sample size N . The conjugate extreme value function, $H(c)$, representing the limiting continuous distribution of largest cracks in each component, is thus estimated by $[1 - Pr(\sigma)]$. In principle, a discrete estimate of the underlying pdf, $h(c) = dH(c)/dc$, could thus be obtained from discrete differentiation of this estimate. In practice, even with many of the extensive data sets to be considered here, such discrete differentiation leads to results with excessive noise or variation. Hence, to aid analysis, $Pr(\sigma)$ will be fit here by continuous smoothing functions, $H(\mu)$, expressed in terms of a continuous variable μ , the relative position within the $H(\mu)$ domain:

$$\mu = \frac{\sigma - \sigma_{\min}}{\sigma_{\max} - \sigma_{\min}}. \quad (12)$$

The values σ_{\min} and σ_{\max} are empirical fitting parameters defining the maximum and minimum limits of the smoothing domain, $0 \leq \mu \leq 1$. It is anticipated that σ_{\min} and σ_{\max} will approximate the observed strength edf bounds σ_1 and σ_N , respectively. The group crack length cdf is then approximated by continuous $H(c) \approx 1 - H(\mu)$, and in the case of stochastic extreme value size effect, the population cdf is thus, $F(c) = [1 - H(\mu)]^{1/k}$, from Eq. (9). In all cases, the group crack length pdf is given by continuous differentiation, $h(c) \approx d[1 - H(\mu)]/dc$, and in the case of stochastic size effect, the population pdf, $f(c) = d[1 - H(\mu)]^{1/k}/dc$, following Eq. (4).

Two simple functional forms will be used here as smoothing functions for experimental $Pr(\sigma)$. The first function is a perturbed sigmoid based on the beta function, used previously in strength and crack length analyses (Cook and DeIRio, 2019ab, Cook *et al.*, 2019):

$$H(\mu) = 30(\mu^{3p}/3 - \mu^{4p}/2 + \mu^{5p}/5), \quad (13)$$

where p is an empirical fitting parameter of order unity that controls the sigmoid symmetry. The second function is a perturbed linear variation, introduced in the crack-length analysis (Cook, 2020), based on smoothly-interpolated linear and power-law functions, $h_i(\mu)$:

$$\begin{aligned}
 h_1(\mu) &= a_1\mu, \\
 h_2(\mu) &= a_2\mu + b, \\
 h_3(\mu) &= (a_3\mu - \mu^{a_3})/(a_3 - 1), \\
 h_4(\mu) &= [h_1(\mu)^{p_1} + h_2(\mu)^{p_1}]^{1/p_1}, \\
 H(\mu) &= [h_3(\mu)^{p_2} + h_4(\mu)^{p_2}]^{1/p_2},
 \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

where a_i and b are empirical fitting parameters of order unity that control linearity and perturbation and p_i are empirical fitting parameters that control interpolation. The $H(\mu)$ functions in Eqs. (13) and (14) are bounded, such that $H(0) = 0$ and $H(1) = 1$, and exhibit zero derivative and negative curvature at the upper bound, $H'(1) = 0$ and $H''(1) < 0$. The difference between the two is that, as a classic sigmoid, Eq. (13) can encapsulate long tail behavior and exhibits zero derivative and positive curvature at the lower bound, $H'(0) = 0$ and $H''(0) > 0$. Equation (14) encapsulates the characteristics of a heavy linear tail and exhibits the opposite behavior: positive derivative and zero curvature at the lower bound, $H'(0) > 0$ and $H''(1) = 0$. As will be seen, the perturbed linear behavior of Eq. (14) describes the majority of particle strength observations. In fact, in many cases, $a_1 \approx b \approx 0$, describing a single, dominant, linear trend. In some cases, in addition, $a_2 \approx a_3/(a_3 - 1)$, describing a dominant curved trend. The fitting of Eqs. (13) and (14) to $Pr(\sigma)$ observations and generation of $H(\mu)$ for subsequent differentiation to obtain $h(c)$ are easily performed numerically, and these were the procedures here.

FIG. 11. Crack length probability density function, pdf, plots, $f(c)$, for the materials tested in bending in Fig. 4. The distributions all have light tails that tend to zero at large crack lengths, *cf* Figs. 7(g) and (h).

FIG. 12. Crack length probability density function, pdf, plots, $f(c)$, for the materials tested in tension and compression in Fig. 5. The distributions all have light tails that tend to zero at large crack lengths, cf Figs. 7(g) and (h).

The solid lines in Figs. 4 and 5 are best-fit sigmoidal responses, Eq. (13), to the large specimen strength distribution data. The solid lines in Fig. 6 are best-fit perturbed linear or curved responses, Eq. (14), to particle strength distributions. In both cases, the smoothing functions, $H(\mu)$, describe the $Pr(\sigma)$ data extremely well over the strength domains. **Figure 11** shows the population crack length pdf responses, $f(c)$, deconvoluted from the large specimen bending strength observations, Fig. 4, using the $H(\mu)$ best-fits as described above and assuming a stochastic size effect and $k = 2$ (k value used here for illustration is typical, see below). The populations are all characterized by relative domains of approximately four, *i.e.*, $c_{\max} \approx 4c_{\min}$, supporting asymmetric probability densities with modal values close to the minimum value, $\approx 1.1c_{\min}$, the majority of the population found between c_{\min} and $0.5c_{\max}$, and long, light tails, very close to $f \approx 0$, extending to c_{\max} . The B values used reflected the toughness of the materials considered, leading to inferred crack lengths of order tens of micrometers, typical of advanced structural ceramics, and re-ordering of some strength and crack length domains, *e.g.*, silicon nitride has greater strength *and* larger flaws relative to glass. **Figure 12(a)** shows population crack length pdf responses, $f(c)$, similarly deconvoluted from the large specimen tensile strength observations, Fig. 5. Except for the B values used, implying crack lengths of order hundreds of nanometers, typical of ultra-strong crystalline fibers, the populations are similar to those observed in large-specimen bending: relative domains with $c_{\max} \approx 4c_{\min}$, asymmetric probability densities with modal values $\approx 1.1c_{\min}$, majority of the population between c_{\min} and $0.5c_{\max}$, and long, light tails, very close to $f \approx 0$, extending to c_{\max} . **Figure 12(b)** shows population crack length pdf responses, $f(c)$, similarly deconvoluted from the large specimen compressive strength observations, Fig. 5. Here the B values were used to imply crack lengths of order one millimeter, typical of porous or quasi-porous materials in crushing. Comparison of Fig. 12(b) with Figs. 11 and 12(a) shows that the populations are similar to those observed in large-specimen bending and tension: $c_{\max} \approx 4c_{\min}$, modal values $\approx 1.1c_{\min}$, majority of population between c_{\min} and $0.5c_{\max}$, and long, light tails, very close to $f \approx 0$, extending to c_{\max} . The observations of Figs. 11 and 12 imply that the strength-controlling flaw populations of large specimens tested in bending, tension or compression are typified by these characteristics.

FIG. 13. Crack length probability density function, pdf, plots, $f(c)$, for the materials tested as particles in Fig. 6. The distributions all have extended heavy tails that tend to non-zero values at large crack lengths, *cf* Figs. 7(i) and (j).

The strength-controlling flaw populations of particles tested in diametral loading are completely different. **Figure 13** shows the population crack length pdf responses, $f(c)$, deconvoluted from the particle strength observations, Fig. 6, using the same procedure as above. The populations are all characterized by large relative domains of approximately 30 or more, *i.e.*, $c_{\max} \approx 30c_{\min}$, supporting extremely asymmetric probability densities with modal values very close to the minimum value, $\approx 1.01c_{\min}$, the majority of the population constricted between c_{\min} and $0.2c_{\max}$, and heavy tails, at clearly non-zero values, $f \approx f_{\max}/30$, extending to c_{\max} . The B values used reflected the toughness of the materials considered, leading to implied crack lengths of order a few millimeters, typical of particles (see below), and re-ordering of some strength and crack length domains, *e.g.*, salt exhibits less strength than corundum with comparable flaw size.

The observations of Fig. 13 imply that the populations of strength controlling flaws in particles are not the same as those of large specimens. In particular, particle flaw populations are much broader. This characteristic and others are more easily observed using logarithmic coordinates, as shown in **Fig. 14**, which plots the same flaw populations for bending specimens and particles shown earlier in Figs. 11 and 13. The outstanding feature of Fig. 14 is the now readily apparent difference in shape of the bending specimen and particle flaw populations. For bending specimens, the population mode crack length values are well defined, and the majority of the population is localized about these values. At larger crack lengths, the population density decreases substantially, with near exponential dependence, $f \sim e^{-c}$, indicated by the solid line as a guide to the eye. For particle specimens, the population modes are weakly defined, and the majority of the population is contained in crack lengths greater than the mode values. At larger crack lengths, the population density decreases slowly, with near inverse linear dependence, $f \sim 1/c$, indicated by the solid line. Particle flaw populations are thus distinctively marked by “heavy” extended tails (slower than exponential decay) and this observation is a key finding of this work.

The above analysis is applied in four levels of increasing complexity to the particle strength distributions reviewed here. At the lowest level, extending to all observations, the digitized data are converted to unbiased $Pr(\sigma)$ edf plots, as in Fig. 6. In many cases, these “raw” data are simply presented to display the diversity of responses for different materials. At the next level, for very small particles, the particles are assumed to contain a single flaw such that $k = 1$. In these cases, the measured strengths are assumed to represent the flaw population identically and this possibility was a major motivation for the review. Next, for some groups of different sized particles of the

same material, the underlying flaw population is assumed to be invariant, such that Eq. (11) pertains, and k varies. In these cases, the measured strengths represent a stochastic size effect; exploration of this commonly assumed phenomenon was also a motivation for the review. Next, for other groups of different sized particles of the same material, the underlying flaw populations are assumed to be related; a common σ_{\max} and therefore c_{\min} will be assumed. Finally, for many groups of different sized particles of the same material, the flaw populations are assumed to be independent. In these last two cases, the measured strengths represent clear deterministic size effects. To enable easy comparisons of the deconvoluted flaw populations and heavy tail effects, the logarithmic plotting scheme of Fig. 14 will be used frequently.

FIG. 14. Plots in logarithmic coordinates illustrating the significant difference between the crack length probability density functions, $f(c)$, for materials tested (a) in tension, from Fig. 11, and (b) as particles, from Fig. 13. Large tensile specimens exhibit light tails that decay exponentially (gray line). Particles exhibit extended heavy tails characterized by inverse linear behavior (gray line).

IV. STRENGTHS: SMALL PARTICLES

Strength distribution studies of particles designated here as “small,” with diameters $D < 1$ mm, illustrate many of the phenomena to be observed throughout this review, particularly the influences on strength of heavy tails and deterministic perturbations of flaw populations. The phenomena are introduced sequentially.

A. Alumina

As part of a larger study of particle size degradation during erosive machining (Slikkerveer *et al.*, 2000), Verspui *et al.* (1997) determined the strength distribution of 44 μm Al_2O_3 particles with a custom testing apparatus. The strength edf $Pr(\sigma)$ constructed from the published results is shown in Fig. 15(a) and exhibits the typical particle behaviors of a linear trend at small strengths, an extended tail at large strengths, and an extremely large ratio of the maximum/minimum strengths. The symbols in Fig. 15(a) represent individual strength measurements and the solid line represents a smooth best-fit of Eq. (14), setting $a_1 = b = 0$ consistent with the single dominant initial linear trend (for brevity here and throughout, in the text and figures, representative particle sizes are used). The conjugate crack length pdf $f(c)$ determined from the strength data using the best fit and the analysis above is shown in Fig. 15(b) (note linear coordinates), using $k = 1$, assuming a single flaw/particle in these small particles, and a representative value of $B = 0.5$ MPa $\text{m}^{1/2}$, typical for oxide interfaces in air (Cook, 2015), that also specifies the maximum flaw size of about 20 μm . The conjugate nature of $Pr(\sigma)$ and $f(c)$ is illustrated by the gray shaded regions in Fig. 15 for $\sigma < 0.5$ GPa corresponding to $c > 1$ μm : the small strength, near-linear region of the strength distribution corresponds to the large crack, heavy tail region of the flaw population (which extends beyond the plot to about 20 μm). The unshaded regions in Fig. 15 for $\sigma > 0.5$ GPa and $c < 1$ μm highlight the extended large strength tail and the dominant peak, or modal crack length, in the flaw population: the peak in Fig. 15(b) is not obvious from Fig. 15(a), consistent with the discussion of Fig. 7 regarding the relationship between flaw populations and strength distributions determined by the analysis above.

FIG. 15. Strength behavior and underlying flaw population of small alumina particles, $D = 44.2 \mu\text{m}$, number of specimens, $N = 81$ (Verspui *et al.*,1997). (a) Empirical distribution function (edf) plot of strength measurements, $Pr(\sigma)$. (b) Crack length probability density function, pdf, plot, $f(c)$. Here and throughout: symbols represent values constructed from published data, lines represent analysis from section III.

B. Quartz sand

Motivated by the geological importance of particle fracture during compaction of sandstones and sands, [Brzesowsky *et al.* \(2011\)](#) determined the strength distribution of ($D = 115, 196, 275,$ and 378) μm sand (predominantly quartz) particles with a conventional testing apparatus. The strength edf $Pr(\sigma)$ curves constructed from the published results are shown in [Fig. 16\(a\)](#) and exhibit another set of typical particle strength characteristics: For an individual distribution, there was a linear trend at small strengths perturbed by a short curved tail at large strengths leading to a moderate (< 5) ratio of the maximum/minimum strength. For the collection of distributions, there was a shift in the threshold strength to smaller values and a narrowing of the distribution as particle size increased. The symbols in Fig. 16(a) represent individual strength measurements—the values are much smaller than those originally reported by [Brzesowsky *et al.* \(2011\)](#) as the **HO** equation was used to determine the representative particle center stress at failure. The values do not affect the observations here. The solid lines represent smooth best-fits of Eq. (14) setting $a_1 = b = 0$. The conjugate crack length pdf $f(c)$ curves determined from the strength data using the best fits and the analysis above are shown in [Fig. 16\(b\)](#), using $k = 1$ and $B = 0.5 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$, typical for solid oxides in air. Compared with Fig. 15, the narrower strength distributions here give rise to narrower implied flaw populations that are all multi- μm in size, reflecting the lesser strengths, and are all $< D$. Although the flaw populations in Fig. 16(b) are very similar, there is a gradual shift to larger crack lengths as the particle size increases. The characteristics suggest that the strength behavior for these particles is predominantly determined by stochastic size effects with a small perturbation by a deterministic size effect leading to additional large cracks added to the flaw population for larger particles.

FIG. 16. Strength behavior and underlying flaw populations of small silica sand particles, $D = (115 \pm 9, 196 \pm 16, 275 \pm 25, \text{ and } 378 \pm 22) \mu\text{m}$, total number of specimens, $N_{\text{tot}} = 262$ (Brzesowsky *et al.*, 2011). (a) Empirical distribution function (edf) plot of strength measurements, $Pr(\sigma)$. (b) Crack length probability density function, pdf, plots, $f(c)$.

C. Survey of material behavior

In order to demonstrate the ability of commercial instruments to perform mechanical testing at small scales, Ribas *et al.* (2014) determined the strength distributions of particles, about 45 μm in diameter, from a diverse set of six materials, Figs. 17(a) and 17(b). The extended tail behavior exhibited by the limestone was similar to that of the alumina in Fig. 15(a), the near-linear behaviors exhibited by the rice husk ash, coal shale, blast furnace slag, and quartz were similar to the sand in Fig. 16(a), and the highly curved response of the SiC was similar to the bauxite of Fig. 6(c), although with the addition of a minor bi-linear region at small crack lengths. Similar results were obtained by Dang *et al.* (2019) on (7 to 17) μm Li-Ni-Mn-Co-O particles using a flat punch indentation system. Conversely, measurements using a custom instrument were performed by Pejchal *et al.* (2017 and 2018) to determine the strength distributions of (20 to 60) μm SiO₂ particles and amorphous or nanocrystalline near-eutectic 45 μm Al₂O₃-ZrO₂-SiO₂ ceramic particles (a-Eu or nc-Eu), Fig. 17(c). In these cases, the distributions are represented as lines (as published) and exhibit dominant near-linear intermediate strength responses and clear bi-linear perturbations at small strengths. In order to explore potential ductility in ceramic particles, Herre *et al.* (2017) used commercial instrumentation in an electron microscope to determine strength distributions of TiO₂ particles, about 600 nm in diameter, Fig. 17(d). The mixed as-processed (AP) and anatase phases exhibited near-linear behavior and the rutile phase exhibited the bi-linear response observed in Fig. 17(b); the strengths were similar to those observed for similar sized particles by Sikong *et al.* (1990), Fig. 3(f). In all cases in Fig. 17 the symbols represent individual strength measurements. The lines through the SiC and rutile data are best fits using unconstrained Eq. (14) to accommodate the observed changes in derivative at small strengths.

FIG. 17. Strength behavior of small particles. (a) and (b) Ribas *et al.* (2014) $D = (45 \pm 3) \mu\text{m}$, $N_{\text{tot}} = 304$. (c) Pejchal *et al.* (2017, 2018) $D = (20 \text{ to } 60)$ and $(25 \text{ to } 35) \mu\text{m}$, $N_{\text{tot}} = 108$. (d) Herre *et al.* (2017) $D = (633 \pm 15, 548 \pm 14, \text{ and } 533 \pm 22) \text{ nm}$, $N_{\text{tot}} = 134$.

D. Flaw populations

The similarities and differences in the small particle flaw populations are made clear in Fig. 18. Logarithmic coordinates, as in Fig. 14, are used to plot pdf $f(c)$ variations obtained from the best-fits to the strength data in Figs. 15, 16, and 17, using the k and B values as above and $k = 1$ and $B = 0.1 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$ (SiC) or $B = 0.7 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$ (rutile). The latter B values ensured that the largest inferred crack lengths were less than the particle size. All the flaw populations are dominated by sub-mm, and in some cases sub- μm , cracks. The broad strength distributions of Al_2O_3 and SiC are reflected in the broad crack length populations occupying most Fig. 18. The linear “kinks” in the strength distributions at small strengths appear in the flaw populations of Fig. 18 as kinks at large crack lengths within a population. The flaw population of the rutile is more narrow but similar in shape, including the large crack kink, reflecting a similarly-shaped but more narrow strength distribution. Conversely, the flaw populations for the sand particles are not as well defined at either large or small crack extremes and do not include the large crack kink. The flaws causing failure in the sand and SiC particle are very small relative to the particle size, whereas those causing failure in the rutile particles are comparable in size to the particles.

Many of the features observed here in strength distributions of small particles will also be observed throughout this review in other, larger, particle systems. These features include: extended large strength tails (Figs. 15 and 17), near linear small strength responses (Figs. 15, 16, and 17), deterministic perturbation of flaw populations (Fig. 16), and bi-linear strength distributions (Fig. 17). The examination of larger particles will require relaxation of the assumption that there is only one flaw/particle ($k = 1$) and thus strength distributions will reflect stochastic size effects ($k > 1$).

FIG. 18. Plot in logarithmic coordinates of crack length probability density functions, $f(c)$, for the small particle flaw populations from Figs. 15, 16, and 17. The Al_2O_3 and SiC particles exhibit very broad populations with extended heavy tails characterized by inverse linear behavior at large crack lengths. The SiO_2 particles exhibit very similar compact populations indicative of a weak particle size effect.

V. STRENGTHS: MEDIUM PARTICLES

Strength distribution studies of particles designated here as “medium,” with diameters predominantly in the domain $1 \text{ mm} < D < 10 \text{ mm}$, constitute the majority of particle studies and hence the majority of studies reported in this review. These studies provide clear examples of material effects, deterministic size effects, and stochastic size effects. The section begins with a survey of strength distribution studies of similar-sized particles of different materials, providing some historical context. This is followed by in-depth examinations of medium particles from two material systems, limestone and quartz, both of which exhibit both deterministic and stochastic size effects on strength. There is overlap with the sections examining small particles and large particles.

A. Survey of material behavior

Early work by [King and Bourgeois \(1993\)](#) described the development and application of an ultra-fast load cell in instrumented impact of particles by a falling metal sphere. King and Bourgeois used the resulting measurements to determine the distribution of specific failure energies, E_m , for a range of materials. The strength edf $Pr(\sigma)$ curves for copper ore and gold ore particles, 3.35 mm to 4.00 mm in diameter, constructed from the published results using the analysis described above, are shown in [Fig. 19\(a\)](#) (other systems will be considered below). The ore strengths exhibit typical particle characteristics of a linear trend at small strengths perturbed by a short curved tail at large strengths and a moderate maximum/minimum strength ratio. In an extensive follow-up work using the same apparatus, [Tavares and King \(1998\)](#) determined specific failure energies for a wide range of materials, examined particle shape effects, and discussed the many applications of particle strength measurement—including optimizing industrial comminution of particles in mining, which was also a focus of King and Bourgeois. The strength edf $Pr(\sigma)$ curves constructed from some of the published results of Tavares and King are shown in [Fig. 19\(b\)](#) for various mineral particles, 2.0 mm to 2.8 mm in diameter (variations in size will be considered below). The strengths exhibit typical particle characteristics, similar to [Fig. 16\(a\)](#), of a linear trend at small strengths perturbed by a short curved tail at large strengths.

In two works at about the same time, [Bertrand et al. \(1988\)](#) and [Huang et al. \(1995\)](#), had the opposite motivation: prolonging the useful life of intact abrasive particles used in industrial

grinding applications. In these cases, the particles were not natural ores or minerals, but particles engineered by heat treatment of mineral powders, based primarily on corundum (Al_2O_3 , the main chemical constituent of bauxite). Bertrand *et al.* examined four grades of corundum in four size classifications, all exhibiting similar behavior. The strength edf $Pr(\sigma)$ curves constructed from some of the published results obtained by conventional strength testing (Fig. 1) are shown in Fig. 20(a) for the four grades, 2.5 mm in diameter (variations in size will be considered below). The strengths exhibit typical particle characteristics, similar to Fig. 16, of a near-linear trend perturbed by a short curved tail at large strengths. In this case, the maximum/minimum strength ratio is extremely large as the minimum strengths are near zero. Huang *et al.* examined several abrasive particles, mostly corundum based, but including SiC, and measured strength distributions using a counter-rotating roller crushing apparatus (see also Huang *et al.*, 1993). The strength edf $Pr(\sigma)$ curves constructed from some of the published results are shown in Fig. 20(b) for four abrasives, 1.85 mm in diameter (variations in size and shape will be considered below). The strengths exhibit typical particle characteristics, similar to Fig. 20(a), of a near-linear trend perturbed by a short curved tail at large strengths. There are some tendencies to bi-linear behavior at small strengths, but overall the observations of Figs 19 and 20 are similar and point to a similar ability of particle testing to distinguish between materials.

The earliest use of a counter-rotating roller crushing apparatus to measure particle strength appears to be by Brecker (1974), who was motivated by optimizing the condition of abrasive particles used in industrial grinding applications, particularly for metals. Brecker mostly examined corundum-based materials but also considered SiC and examined the effects of deliberate alteration of particle shape. These ideas were all pursued by Huang *et al.* 20 years later. In particular, Huang *et al.* “rounded” brown corundum particles by ball-milling, leading to a slight strengthening, Fig. 20(b). In contrast, Brecker deliberately “ground” flats on alumina particles, leading to significant strengthening, as shown in Fig. 21(a) by the edf $Pr(\sigma)$ plots constructed from the published data for nominal 1.6 mm particles. The implication is that the introduced flats altered the geometry of the particles such that the central biaxial tension was decreased during testing; clearly a deterministic effect, but on stress not flaw population. The implication is supported by the similarity in the shapes of the strength distributions of the as-received (AR) and ground particles, highlighted in the expanded-scale inset of Fig. 21(a) and supporting the idea that the AR flaw population was not altered by grinding.

A feature of the observations of Brecker in Fig. 21(a) is that the strength distributions are wide and highly curved. Similar observations were made by Nakata *et al.* (2001a, 2001b) as part of an extensive geotechnical study of the relationship between uniaxial confined compression behavior of sands and soils and the crushing behavior of the individual constituent particles. Figure 21(b) shows edf $Pr(\sigma)$ plots constructed from the published data for Masado (degraded granite) and silica (probably quartz) sands (Nakata, 2001b) of size 1.4 mm to 1.7 mm measured using a custom quasi-static apparatus. The strength distributions are wide and highly curved, resembling the experimental observations of Figs. 6(c), 17(b), and 21(a), and the simulations of Fig. 7(j), suggesting underlying heavy tailed flaw populations in these cases. Similar data were reported by Todisco *et al.* (2017) for 2.9 mm sand particles crushed between platens and in the original HO (1966) work on rock particles, as shown by Todisco *et al.* in an extensive study of contact shape effects on strength. Additionally, Rozenblat *et al.* (2011) showed similarly-shaped failure load distributions for mm-scale potash and basalt particles as did Salman *et al.* (2002, 2003) in impact failure velocity observations of 5 mm alumina and fertilizer particles. The data of Figs 19, 20, and 21 are ordered by decreasing particle size and, with the exception of Fig. 21(b), exhibit increasing strength, suggesting that for similar materials (these are all minerals) that there are clear size effects (smaller is stronger). The following considers flaw populations and deterministic and stochastic size effects in some detail for strengths of medium sized particles of two frequently tested materials.

FIG. 19. Strength behavior of medium particles. (a) King and Bourgeois (1993) $D = (3.35 \text{ to } 4.00) \text{ mm}$, $N_{\text{tot}} = 124$.
 (b) Tavares and King (1998) $D = (2.0 \text{ to } 2.8) \text{ mm}$, $N_{\text{tot}} = 256$.

FIG. 20. Strength behavior of medium alumina particles. (a) *Bertrand et al. (1988)* $D = (2.6 \pm 0.1, 2.7 \pm 0.1, 2.4 \pm 0.1, \text{ and } 2.4 \pm 0.1) \text{ mm}$, $N_{\text{tot}} = 188$. (b) *Huang et al. (1995)* $D = 1.85$ (estimated ± 0.25) mm $N_{\text{tot}} = 275$.

FIG. 21. Strength behavior of medium particles. (a) Alumina, Brecker (1974) $D = 1.6$ mm, $N_{\text{tot}} = 132$. (b) Silica and sand (Nakata, 2001b) $D = (1.4 \text{ to } 1.7)$ mm, $N_{\text{tot}} = 141$.

B. Limestone

Limestone and marble are both composed primarily of the mineral CaCO_3 ; limestone is a sedimentary rock and is typically porous, marble is a metamorphic rock and dense (and was initially limestone). In particle form there is often little difference, although “limestone” may contain a microstructure based on animal shells. The term limestone will be used here for brevity. **Figure 22** shows edf $Pr(\sigma)$ plots constructed from published data from four studies of strength distributions of limestone particles: **Wang *et al.* (2015)** were concerned with particle stability in geotechnical engineering applications, whereas **Rozenblat *et al.* (2011)**, **Barrios *et al.* (2011)**, and **King and Bourgeois (1993)** were concerned with comminution efficiency in materials processing. The individual studies in Fig. 22 are ordered by decreasing minimum particle size. Within a study, as a guide to the eye, the data for particles approximately 5 mm in diameter are indicated by solid symbols, all other data are indicated by open symbols; the particle size for each data set is indicated. As anticipated from the above, the individual studies exhibit a conjugate ordering of increasing strength, indicated by the additional guide of vertical dashed lines at strengths of 15 MPa in each study. The data for each particle size in each study exhibit near-linear trends perturbed by short curved tails at large strengths; similar behavior was observed by **Vogel *et al.* (2002)** in failure energy results obtained on limestone and other materials using an impact mill. Within the studies considered here, the strength distributions are narrower and occur at smaller values for larger particles. In two studies, (a) and (d), the (minimum) threshold strength was unchanged with increased particle size, indicative of a stochastic size effect. In one study, (c), the threshold strength decreased with increased particle size, indicative of a deterministic size effect. The solid lines in Figs. 22(c) represent best-fits of Eq. (14), setting $a_1 = b = 0$ consistent with the single dominant linear trends. The solid lines in Fig. 22(d) represent a similar fit or prediction from Eq. (11). The inferred flaw populations are considered below.

Limestone

FIG. 22. Strength behavior of medium limestone particles. (a) Wang *et al.* (2015) $D = (6 \text{ to } 8 \text{ and } 25 \text{ to } 33) \text{ mm}$, $N_{\text{tot}} = 64$. (b) Rozenblat *et al.* (2011) $D = (4 \text{ to } 5) \text{ mm}$, $N = 97$. (c) Barrios *et al.* (2011) $D = (2.36 \text{ to } 2.83, 4.75 \text{ to } 5.6, 9.5 \text{ to } 11.2, 19.2 \text{ to } 22.4, 37.5 \text{ to } 45.5, \text{ and } 53 \text{ to } 63) \text{ mm}$, $N_{\text{tot}} = 293$. (d) King and Bourgeois (1993) $D = (0.5 \text{ to } 0.7 \text{ and } 4.00 \text{ to } 4.75) \text{ mm}$, $N_{\text{tot}} = 144$.

C. Quartz

Quartz is crystalline SiO_2 and is the most common mineral found at the earth's surface. Most beach sand is composed of quartz particles. The chemical name for SiO_2 is silica. (Fused silica is an amorphous glass that rarely occurs in nature but is commonly used in the semiconductor or MEMS industries, where it is often confusingly referred to as “fused quartz.”) The term quartz will be used here. **Figure 23** shows edf $Pr(\sigma)$ plots constructed from published data from four studies of strength distributions of quartz particles: **King and Bourgeois (1993)** and **Tavares and King. (1998)** were concerned with comminution efficiency in materials processing, **McDowell (2002)** was concerned with compaction of particle aggregates in geotechnical applications, and **Wang and Coop (2016)** included strength measurements in an extensive study using a custom apparatus for particle failure observations. The notation and findings in Fig. 23 are nearly identical to those in Fig. 22: individual studies in Fig. 23 are ordered by decreasing particle size; the data for particles approximately 1 mm in diameter are indicated by solid symbols, all other data are indicated by open symbols; the particle size for each data set is indicated; the individual studies exhibit an ordering of increasing strength, indicated by vertical dashed lines at strengths of 50 MPa; the data for each particle size in each study exhibit near-linear trends perturbed by short curved tails at large strengths; within a study, the strength distributions are narrower and occur at smaller values for larger particles; in two studies in Fig. 23, (a) and (b), the threshold strength was unchanged with increased particle size, indicative of a stochastic size effect; in two studies in Fig. 23, (c) and (d), the threshold strength decreased with increased particle size, indicative of a deterministic size effect; the solid lines in Figs. 23(c) represent best-fits of Eq. (14), setting $a_1 = b = 0$ consistent with the single dominant linear trends. The solid lines in Fig. 23(a) represent a similar fit or prediction from Eq. (11).

FIG. 23. Strength behavior of medium quartz particles. (a) **King and Bourgeois (1993)** $D = (1.4 \text{ to } 1.7 \text{ and } 3.35 \text{ to } 4.00) \text{ mm}$, $N_{\text{tot}} = 147$. (b) **Wang and Coop (2016)** $D = (1.18 \text{ to } 2.36 \text{ and } 2.36 \text{ to } 5.00) \text{ mm}$, $N_{\text{tot}} = 164$. (c) **Tavares and King. (1998)** $D = (0.25 \text{ to } 0.35, 0.5 \text{ to } 0.7, 1 \text{ to } 1.18, 2 \text{ to } 2.8, \text{ and } 4 \text{ to } 4.75) \text{ mm}$, $N_{\text{tot}} = 354$, **McDowell (2002)** $D = (0.3 \text{ to } 0.6, 0.6 \text{ to } 1.18, \text{ and } 1.18 \text{ to } 2.00), \text{ mm}$, $N_{\text{tot}} = 87$.

D. Extreme value size effects

The deterministic and stochastic size effects observed for each material in Figs. 22 and 23 are now examined in turn. The simplest and least biased method of analyzing the strength distribution data in Figs. 22(c) and 23(c) is to assess the distributions independently in terms of underlying extreme value flaw pdf variations, $h(c)$. Relationships between the $h(c)$ variations thus generated can then indicate in an unbiased way the details of any deterministic size effects, similar to the interpretation of the $f(c)$ variations of Fig. 16(b). For the small alumina particles considered in Fig. 16(b), $k = 1$ was reasonably assumed such that $h(c) \rightarrow f(c)$. Here, the particles are larger, k is unknown, and the analysis above was thus restricted to the determination of the $h(c)$ variations. The smooth $H(\mu)$ strength fits in Figs. 22(c) and 23(c) for the limestone and quartz particles were used in $h(c)$ determinations subject to two constraints: A single value of B was used for each material and the largest inferred flaw was smaller than the largest particle. A critical internal consistency check is that the maximum flaw size $<$ particle size constraint is then true for all other particles with the single selected single value of B . The resulting extreme value flaw populations are shown in identical logarithmic coordinates in Fig. 24, using (a) $B = 0.4 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$ for limestone and (b) $B = 0.5 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$ for quartz. The solid straight lines are guides to the eye of slope -1 , *i.e.*, are of form c^{-1} .

The extreme value flaw populations $h(c)$ for both materials in Fig. 24 are similar and consist of smooth rounded variations with modes asymmetrically located between steep decreases to minima and extended decreases with near c^{-1} variation to maxima. The maxima are internally consistent with the single values of B set by the largest particles. The modes, minima, and maxima all decrease with decreasing particle size, more so for quartz than limestone, although the form of the populations in both cases, including the maximum/minimum ratio, is relatively invariant. The different $h(c)$ variations of Fig. 24 clearly demonstrate a deterministic size effect, although it is also clear that the underlying flaw populations, $f(c, D)$, that depend on particle size are related. The simplest explanation is that for the largest particles the *base* population of flaws, from which the extreme values are sampled in a strength test, is given by the outer envelope of the responses of all the particles. That is, $f(c, 4)$ for quartz, Fig 24(b), extends from about 0.01 mm to 4 mm with a dominant c^{-1} variation; $h(c, 4)$, which reflects the *extreme* flaws from each 4 mm particle, extends from about 0.5 mm to 4 mm. Decreasing the particle size truncates upper bound of the base flaw

population, such that $f(c, 2)$ extends from about 0.01 mm to 2 mm with the same dominant c^{-1} variation; $h(c, 2)$, which reflects the extreme flaws from each 2 mm particle, appears in logarithmic coordinates as a simply shifted variation extending from about 0.2 mm to 2 mm; the apparent shifts continue for the 1 mm, 0.5 mm, and 0.25 mm particles. The observed strength distributions thus reflect a deterministic size effect in which particle size determines the upper bound of the flaw population. Similar behavior with similar explanation is observed for the limestone, with differences in the quantitative details: $f(c, 63)$ for limestone, Fig 24(a), extends from about 0.1 mm to 60 mm (off graph) with a dominant c^{-1} variation, and so on. Greater consideration is given below (Section VIII) to the scaling of maximum flaw size with D in deterministic systems.

In contrast, another simple method of analyzing strength distribution data, shown in Figs. 22(d) and 23(a), is to assume that the distributions are *not* independent and that the underlying extreme value flaw pdf variations, $h(c)$, are related by stochastic size effects. The key observation that leads to this assumption is that the observed threshold strengths for different particle sizes are identical, raising the possibility that the strength distributions are related by Eq. (11). Although the average number of flaws in each size particle, k_i , is unknown, the exponent in Eq. (11) provides the ratio of related particle sizes, k_j/k_i . Hence, the (wider) strength distributions of the smaller particles, 0.5 mm for limestone and 1.40 mm for quartz, were fit as described to arrive at $H_1(\sigma)$ for each material. The (contracted) strength distributions for the larger particles, 4 mm for limestone and 3.35 mm for quartz, $H_2(\sigma)$, were then predicted as per Eq. (11) treating k_2/k_1 as a fitting variable. The predictions are shown as the solid lines in Figs. 22(d) and 23(a) using $k_2/k_1 = 2.85$ and $k_2/k_1 = 2.30$ for limestone and quartz, respectively. Consistency with stochastic size effects in these systems is observed in two ways: First, mathematically, the data are well described by Eq. 11, based on flaw independence, as indicated by the solid lines. Second, physically, the exponents k_2/k_1 are comparable to the ratios of the separately measured particle sizes, given in the Figures. For example, for quartz, $3.35/1.40 \approx 2.30$. Greater consideration is given below (section VIII) to the scaling of k_j/k_i with particle size in stochastic systems.

FIG. 24. Illustration of deterministic size effects in flaw distributions: Plots in logarithmic coordinates of separate crack length probability density functions, $h(c)$, for the medium particles from (a) Fig. 22(c), limestone and (b) Fig. 23(c), quartz. The solid lines indicate c^{-1} trends. In both cases, $h(c)$ shifts to larger flaws as particle size (given in mm) increases.

A guide to the invariant underlying flaw populations $f(c)$ for each material can be gained by setting $k_1 = 1$ to infer the populations from the $H_1(\sigma)$ fits. As above, the fits in each case were subject to the constraint that the value of B used led to the largest inferred flaws smaller than the largest particle. The resulting flaw populations are shown in Fig. 25, using $B = 0.23 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$ for limestone and $B = 0.25 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$ for quartz. The solid straight line is a guide to the eye of form c^{-1} . The resulting populations are similar in form to those of Fig. 24 but are now invariant and pertain to variable particle size. A third, positive, consistency check is that these inferred B values are comparable to the toughness values of the materials (Lawn, 1993; Cook, 2015) and similar analyses, Fig. 24.

FIG. 25. Outcome of stochastic size effect analysis: Plot in logarithmic coordinates of crack length population probability density functions, $f(c)$, for the medium particles from Fig. 22(d), limestone, Fig. 23(a), quartz, and Fig. 25, Quiou sand. The solid lines indicate c^{-1} trends. In all cases, single crack length populations $f(c)$ describe the behavior at all particle sizes through probabilistic effects.

E. Quiou sand

A striking example of strength distributions formed by stochastic size effects can be observed in the experiments by McDowell and Amon (2000) on Quiou sand particles. Quiou sand is a calcareous, limestone-based, sand from Brittany, France. Motivated by considerations of compaction of soil grain aggregates, McDowell and Amon used a custom compression apparatus to test the strengths of carefully graded Quiou sand particles from 1 mm to 16 mm in size. Figure 26 shows the strength edf $Pr(\sigma)$ plots constructed from the published data. Separate panels, scaled to the strength domain of each size particle, show as symbols strength measurements of individual particles of each size; the inset shows a comparison of the different particle sizes at the same scale. The inset makes clear that the strength distributions for the different size particles have a common threshold, consistent with a stochastic size effect. The panels make clear that the strength distributions are of very similar, curved concave shape, and that the thresholds are very small values, consistent with the observed maximum/minimum strength ratio in each case of about 20 or greater. As above, the (largest) strength distribution of the smallest 1 mm particles was fit to arrive at $H_1(\sigma)$, shown as the bold solid line, constrained by the minimum strength, σ_{\min} , of the largest 16 mm particles, about 0.2 MPa. The strength distributions for the larger particles, $H_2(\sigma)$ for 2 mm, $H_4(\sigma)$ for 4 mm, and $H_{8,16}(\sigma)$ for 8 mm and 16 mm, were then predicted as per Eq. (11) treating only k_j/k_1 as a fitting variable in each case; the minimum strength was fixed. The predictions are shown as the fine solid lines using $k_2/k_1 = 3$, $k_4/k_1 = 50$, and $k_{8,16}/k_1 = 300$ for 2 mm, 4 mm, and (8 and 16) mm, particles respectively. For maximum strengths varying by approximately a factor of 100, the predicted variations are entirely consistent, both qualitatively and quantitatively, with stochastic size effects in this system leading to significant decreases in strength with increasing particle size. The single underlying flaw population for this material can be estimated by setting $k_1 = 1$ to infer the population $f(c)$ from the $H_1(\sigma)$ fit, subject to the constraint of $B = 0.2 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$ to generate a largest flaw smaller than the largest particle. The resulting flaw population is shown in Fig. 25 and is similar in shape to those of the other medium particles considered here: rounded modal section adjacent to a steep decline to a minimum flaw size and an extended decrease to a maximum flaw size. In this case, the domain extends over a factor of 10^4 in flaw size, from about 10 mm to 0.001 mm, consistent with the large strength variation, Fig. 26. Unlike the examples of Fig. 24, here all particle strength are formed from the same population of

flaws. The 1 mm particles, which probably contain only one flaw, exhibit strengths representing the entire flaw population, whereas the 16 mm particles, which contain many flaws, are restricted by extreme value sampling to exhibit strengths representing only flaws from about 10 mm to 1 mm. Although it is clear that this is stochastic system, it is also clear that the number of flaws/particle is a greater than linear function of particle size, *e.g.*, $300 > (16 \text{ mm}/1 \text{ mm})$, $50 > (4 \text{ mm}/1 \text{ mm})$. This point is considered further below (Section VIII).

FIG. 26. Strength behavior of medium Quiou sand particles **McDowell and Amon (2000)** $D = (0.66 \text{ to } 0.996, 1.43 \text{ to } 2.01, 3.33 \text{ to } 4.41, 7.22 \text{ to } 8.5, \text{ and } 14.7 \text{ to } 16.3) \text{ mm}$, $N_{\text{tot}} = 146$. Inset shows composite response at all sizes. The solid lines represent stochastic size effect predictions from the single flaw population shown in Fig. 25.

VI. STRENGTHS: LARGE PARTICLES

Strength distribution studies of particles designated here as “large,” with diameters predominantly in the domain $D > 10$ mm, although infrequent, provide clear examples of material and deterministic size effects. This section is structured similarly to that for the medium particles and begins with presentation of strength distribution studies of different-sized large particles of similar and different materials. This is followed by in-depth examinations of large particles from two rock systems, both of which exhibit deterministic size effects on strength. There is overlap with the section examining medium particles.

A. Railway ballast

Railway ballast is a layer of aggregated angular rocks beneath railroad tracks, providing elastic foundation, noise absorption, and fluid removal by percolation between the rock particles. Repeated train loading leads to ballast degradation by crushing of ballast particles, with clear performance and economic implications. Two studies have considered strength distributions of railway ballast particles, which are here considered large. In an extensive study, [Lim *et al.* \(2004\)](#) used a conventional loading platen geometry (Fig. 1) to observe and measure the strength behavior of six different ballast rocks separated into three different size classes. As an example of the results, the strength edf $Pr(\sigma)$ curves for the granitic rock, constructed from the published results using the analysis described above, is shown in [Fig. 27\(a\)](#). The strengths exhibit typical particle characteristics of a linear trend at small strengths perturbed by a short curved tail at large strengths and a moderate maximum/minimum strength ratio. As the particle size was increased, the strength distributions became narrower and the threshold strengths shifted to smaller values; the latter observation a clear indication of a deterministic size effect. In another extensive study, [Koohmishi and Palassi \(2016\)](#) used localized probe diametral loading (reminiscent of the HO simulations) to observe and measure the strength behavior of four different ballast rocks separated into three different shape classes (reminiscent of the early Brecker study) and sieved into four different size classes. No significant effect of shape on strength was observed, although there was a clear effect of size and rock type. An example of the results, the strength edf $Pr(\sigma)$ curves constructed from the published results using the analysis described above is shown in [Fig. 27\(b\)](#). The strengths for

the different rocks exhibit typical particle characteristics of a linear trend at small strengths perturbed by a short, curved tail at large strengths and a moderate maximum/minimum strength ratio. Size and material effects are evident. The implication of the results from the two studies shown in Fig. 27 is that very large, angular, fragments that might be regarded as “rocks” exhibit strength distributions identical to those of small, rounded, objects identified as “particles” (*e.g.*, Figs. 17, 19). At all sizes, particles exhibit strength distributions clearly distinct from “large” specimens (Figs. 4 and 5).

B. Quarry rocks

In an extensive study considering composition, microstructure, wear, and fracture properties of Brazilian quarry rocks for geotechnical applications, [Tavares and das Neves \(2008\)](#) used a ball-drop impact tester to measure specific failure energy distributions of rock particles of seven different sizes from four different quarries. [Figure 28](#) shows edf $Pr(\sigma)$ plots, constructed from the published data using the analysis described above, of rocks from two different quarries, the Santa Luzia (SL series) and the Vigné (V series). Although in some cases the “particles” are quite large (90 mm), and the size range is greater than a factor of 100, the strength distributions exhibit by-now typical particle characteristics: a linear trend at small strengths perturbed by a short curved tail at large strengths, moderate maximum/minimum strength ratios, and narrower domains with smaller thresholds as the particle size was increased. The symbols in Fig. 28 represent individual failure measurements and the lines represent best fits of Eq. (14) to the data, setting $a_1 = b = 0$ consistent with the single dominant linear trends. All particle sizes were fit independently, consistent with the clear indication of a deterministic size effect in the shifted thresholds.

The extreme value flaw sub-populations, $h(c)$, were determined from the smooth $H(\mu)$ strength fits for the SL and V series particles in Fig. 28, subject to the constraints that a single value of B was used for each series and that the largest inferred flaw in each series was smaller than the largest particle size. The resulting sub-populations are shown using identical logarithmic coordinates in [Fig. 29](#), using $B = 0.5 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$ for both the SL and V series. The solid straight lines are guides to the eye of form c^{-1} . These deconvoluted $h(c)$ curves are similar in shape to those of the medium particles presented in Figs. 24 and 25, reflecting, as discussed above, similarly shaped strength distribution measurements, Figs. 22, 23, and 26. The $h(c)$ curves have a rounded modal section

adjacent to a steep decline to a minimum flaw size and an extended decrease to a maximum flaw size. As with the limestone and quartz flaws of Fig. 24, here the modes, minima, and maxima also decrease with decreasing particle size and the form of the populations is relatively invariant, although slightly different for the different series (SL is broader than V). Also similar to Fig. 24 is that the $h(c)$ variations of Fig. 29 clearly demonstrate a deterministic size effect in which the underlying particle-size dependent flaw populations, $f(c, D)$, are related. The outer envelope of the responses of all the particles provides an estimate of the base population of flaws, from which the extreme values are sampled in a strength test. Decreasing the particle size truncates the upper bound of the base flaw population, such that $h(c)$ appears in logarithmic coordinates as a simply shifted variation. The observed strength distributions thus reflect a deterministic size effect in which particle size determines the upper bound of the flaw population and thus the lower bound or threshold of the strength. Similar strength distributions and influences of particle size were reported by [Lobo-Guerrero *et al.* \(2006b\)](#) for two rocks types tested using opposing conical platens and by [Nad and Saramak \(2018\)](#) for three types of copper ore from Poland tested using conventional platens.

FIG. 27 Strength behavior of large railway ballast particles. (a) *Lim et al. (2004)* $D = (10 \text{ to } 14, 20 \text{ to } 28, \text{ and } 37.5 \text{ to } 50) \text{ mm}$, $N_{\text{tot}} = 90$. (b) *Koohmishi and Palassi (2016)* $D = (50 \text{ to } 62.5, 19 \text{ to } 25, \text{ and } 37.5 \text{ to } 50, \text{ and } 25 \text{ to } 37.5) \text{ mm}$, $N_{\text{tot}} = 252$.

FIG. 28. Strength behavior of large quarry rock particles. Tavares and das Neves (2008) $D = (0.59 \text{ to } 0.7, 1.18 \text{ to } 1.4, 2.36 \text{ to } 2.83, \text{ and } 4.75 \text{ to } 5.6, 13.3 \text{ to } 16, 37.5 \text{ to } 45, \text{ and } 75 \text{ to } 90) \text{ mm}$. (a) Santa Luzia (SL series), $N_{\text{tot}} = 317$. (b) Vigné (V series) $N_{\text{tot}} = 256$.

FIG. 29. Illustration of deterministic size effects in flaw distributions: Plots in logarithmic coordinates of separate crack length probability density functions, $h(c)$, for the large rock particles from Fig. 28. For both SL and V series rocks, $h(c)$ shifts to larger flaws as particle size (given in mm) increases. Note the similarity to Fig. 24.

VII. STRENGTHS: ENGINEERED PARTICLES

Most of the particles considered so far, classified by size, have been natural materials, notably quartz-based sand and other minerals (Figs. 3, 16, 17, 19, 21, 22, 23, 26), rocks and ores (Figs. 6, 19, 27, 28), coal (Figs. 3, 17), and salt (Fig. 6). Some, however, have been engineered materials, including agglomerates or aggregates formed from cement, limestone, and sand (Fig. 3), or sintered particles of bauxite, corundum, or alumina (Figs. 6, 20), or other ceramic compounds such as titania, silicon carbide, zirconia-based, and silica (Figs. 17). In this section, attention is focused on engineered particles, beginning with a set of three in-depth quantitative studies of alumina-based materials, demonstrating the transition from deterministic size effects to stochastic size effects in particle strengths. This is followed by a similar quantitative study of the strengths of iron-ore pellets demonstrating a stochastic size effect. The section concludes with presentations of the strength behavior of glass, cement, catalysts, food, ice, and silicon- and carbon-based particles.

A. Alumina Abrasives, Proppants, and Refractories

Due to their superior structural properties, some of the most studied engineered particles consist of alumina-based compounds (Brecker, 1974; Wong *et al.*, 1987; Bertrand *et al.*, 1988; Shipway and Hutchings, 1993; Huang *et al.*, 1993, 1995; Verspui *et al.*, 1997; Tavares and King, 1998; Salman *et al.*, 2002; Müller, 2013; Fedorov and Gulyaeva, 2019). The primary constituent of alumina is Al_2O_3 , properly termed corundum in its single-crystal form (sometimes also known as sapphire or ruby when naturally or artificially doped for color). The term alumina is predominantly reserved for engineered polycrystalline Al_2O_3 materials. These materials also usually contain deliberately-added grain-boundary related microstructural control agents in the form of small amounts of other oxides or glasses. Bauxite is a natural sedimentary rock consisting primarily of aluminum-based minerals, along with some iron and silicate minerals. Bauxite is the principal ore used to form Al_2O_3 powder for aluminum metal production and (less so) for fabrication of polycrystalline alumina components, either macroscopic (*e.g.*, Fig. 3) or particles (*e.g.*, Fig 6). Huang *et al.* (1993, 1995) used both a counter-rotating roller crushing apparatus and a conventional platen apparatus to measure the strength distributions of several different materials of abrasive particles, including a series of polycrystalline alumina particles several mm in size (although termed “corundum” by Huang *et al.*, micrographs clearly show polycrystalline structures). The

intent was to identify, long-lived sharp particles for cutting and machining manufacture operations. *Wong et al. (1987)* used a conventional platen apparatus to measure the strength distributions of two sets of mm-scale particles formed from bauxite precursor sub-particles initially milled to the (5 to 8) μm scale. In the first set, water and starch were used to bind the sub-particles into spherical aggregates that were then dried to form four sizes of particles in the green state. In the second set, half the green state particles of each size were kiln fired, leading to sintering, shrinkage, and near complete transformation to aluminosilicate mullite. In this case, the intent was to identify the passage of defects from the green state to the sintered state. The sintered particles were similar to those used as synthetic proppants during hydraulic fracturing in oil wells. *Bertrand et al. (1988)* used a conventional platen apparatus to measure the strength distributions of four mm-scale sizes of each of four different alumina particles. The particles were commercial materials, differing by microstructure, which consisted of 50 μm -scale grains and included intra- and inter-granular porosity. The goal in this case was to identify optimum particles for use in refractory bricks for high temperature manufacturing. The works on alumina particles of *Huang et al.*, *Wong et al.*, and *Bertrand et al.* illustrate a sequence of increasing constraint on strength distributions as the underlying flaw populations become increasingly related.

FIG. 30. Strength behavior and underlying flaw populations of abrasive corundum particles. [Huang *et al.* \(1993, 1995\)](#) $D = (0.7 \pm 0.15, 1.29 \pm 0.15, 1.85 \pm 0.25, 2.58 \pm 0.30)$ mm (uncertainties estimated), $N_{\text{tot}} = 583$. (a) Empirical distribution function (edf) plot of strength measurements, $Pr(\sigma)$. (b) Crack length probability density function, pdf, plots, $h(c)$, illustrating deterministic size effects. Note the similarity to Figs. 24 and 29.

Figure 30(a) shows edf $Pr(\sigma)$ plots, constructed from the published data using the analysis described above, of four sizes of abrasive particles of a single alumina from the work of Huang *et al* (1995) (other materials from this work were similar, *e.g.*, Figs. 6, 20). The strength distributions exhibit the typical particle characteristics of a linear trend at small strengths perturbed by a short curved tail at large strengths, moderate maximum/minimum strength ratios, with weak tendencies to narrower domains and smaller thresholds as the particle size was increased. The symbols in Fig. 30(a) represent individual failure measurements, The lines represent best fits of Eq. (14) to the data, setting $a_1 = b = 0$ for the larger particles and unconstrained for the smallest particles that exhibited a bi-linear response. All particle sizes were fit independently, consistent with the clear indication of a deterministic size effect in the shifted thresholds. The procedure used to determine the extreme value flaw sub-populations, $h(c)$, from the smooth $H(\mu)$ strength fits for these alumina particles closely follow that described above in the sections discussing medium- and large-size particles The resulting sub-populations are shown in Fig. 30(b), using $B = 1.0 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$ The solid straight line is a guide to the eye of form c^{-1} . These deconvoluted $h(c)$ curves are similar to those of the medium and large quartz, limestone, and rock particles presented in Figs. 24, 25, and 29, reflecting, as discussed above, similarly shaped strength distribution measurements, Figs. 22, 23, and 26-28. The appearance and variation of the modes, maxima, and minima are similar and the form of the populations, although slightly different from those above, is relatively invariant. Also similar is that the $h(c)$ variations of Fig. 30(b) demonstrate a deterministic size effect in which the underlying particle-size dependent flaw populations, $f(c, D)$, are different but related, appearing predominantly as shifts, as in Figs. 24 and 29.

A much closer relationship between particle-size dependent extreme value flaw sub-populations, $h(c)$, drawn from underlying populations, $f(c, D)$, is demonstrated in the work of Wong *et al* (1987) on proppant particles of bauxite. Figure 31 shows edf $Pr(\sigma)$ plots, constructed from the published data using the analysis described above, of the two sets of four sizes of bauxite particles in the green and fired states; there was about 15 % relative dimensional particle shrinkage on firing. The symbols in Fig. 31 represent individual failure measurement and the strengths increased from a few megapascals in the green state, typical of weakly bound agglomerates, *e.g.*, sand, limestone, Fig. 3, and the calcined 1.97 mm alumina granules of Satone *et al.* (2017) (about 6.7 MPa) to a few hundred megapascals in the fired state, typical of solid alumina particles (*e.g.*, Fig. 30). The strength distributions exhibit typical particle characteristics of linear or bi-linear

trends at small strengths perturbed by short curved tails at large strengths and smaller thresholds as the particle size was increased. Two clear features of Fig. 31 are that the strength distributions converged at large strengths in both sets of data and the relative shapes of the distributions were not significantly altered by firing. The lines in Fig. 31 represent best fits of Eq. (14) to the data; for simplicity setting $a_1 = b = 0$ in all cases but constraining the fits to a single maximum fitting strength, σ_{\max} , for each set of particles.

FIG. 31. Strength behavior of proppant bauxite particles. (Wong *et al.* (1987) Empirical distribution function (edf) plots, $Pr(\sigma)$, exhibiting constrained maximum strengths. (a) $D = (1.84 \pm 0.03, 1.48 \pm 0.02, 1.08 \pm 0.02, 0.95 \pm 0.01)$ mm (green). (b) $(1.60 \pm 0.03, 1.32 \pm 0.02, 0.90 \pm 0.01, 0.79 \pm 0.01)$ mm (fired). $N_{\text{tot}} = 380$.

The extreme value flaw sub-populations, $h(c)$, for the bauxite particles were determined from the $H(\mu)$ strength fits as described above for other particles, here using (a) $B = 0.05 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$ for the green set and (b) $B = 1.0 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$ for the fired set, and are shown in Fig. 32. The solid straight lines are guides to the eye of form c^{-1} . The individual deconvoluted bauxite $h(c)$ curves in Fig. 32 are most similar in form to the V-series rock particles presented in Fig. 29, reflecting similarly shaped strength distributions measurements. However, the relationship between the individual curves in Fig. 32 is completely different from that in Fig. 29, reflecting differently constrained strength distributions as a function of particle size. The $h(c)$ variations of Fig. 29 demonstrate a deterministic size effect in which decreasing the particle size truncates the upper bound of the flaw population; stochastic effects truncate the lower bound of the flaw distribution such that $h(c)$ appears in logarithmic coordinates as a shifted variation. Mathematically, in terms of Eq. 9, this requires $k > 1$, *i.e.*, the particles contain multiple flaws. The $h(c)$ variations of Fig. 32 also demonstrate a deterministic size effect in which decreasing the particle size truncates the upper bound of the flaw population. However, the lower bound of the flaw distribution remain invariant with particle size, such that $h(c)$ appears in logarithmic coordinates as a broadened variation from a fixed minimum. In terms of Eq. 9 in this case, $k = 1$ is required, otherwise stochastic effects would lead to weakening as multiple, larger flaws were incorporated into the particles. Figure 32 thus represents one of the hypotheses of this review in that strength tests on particles provide direct insight into flaw populations by circumventing extreme value effects. Mathematically, in Fig. 32, $h(c)$ represents $f(c)$.

Physically, a clear feature of Fig. 32 is that the particle flaw populations in the green and fired states are closely and intuitively related. The flaws in the fired particles (b) are about an order of magnitude smaller than those in the green state (a), reflecting densification but little sub-particle re-arrangement on sintering. This reduction only accounts for about a factor of three increase in strength, consistent with about a factor of 20 increase in toughness on sintering, reflecting the change in binding from weak hydrogen bonds to covalent-ionic bonds. The invariant flaw size minima observed in both states probably reflects a characteristic multi-sub particle interstice formed in the green state and maintained on firing. Similarly, the decreasing flaw size maxima observed as a function of particle size in both states probably reflects large pores formed in the green state and maintained on firing; the implication is that this pore size depends on particle size in a deterministic way. Although the results here address a goal of the original study by Wong *et*

al. (1987) in following the evolution of strength-limiting flaws, the use of unbiased analysis leads to many new quantitative findings. A particular conclusion here is that additional defects are not generated on firing, in contradiction to the earlier inference.

FIG. 32. Underlying flaw populations of proppant bauxite particles from Fig. 31. Crack length probability density function, pdf, plots, $h(c)$, illustrating deterministic size effects with constrained minimum flaw sizes.

The closest relationship between sub-populations of flaws from different particle sizes is the relationship generated by stochastic extreme value effects, Eq. 9, on an invariant underlying population, $f(c)$. This behavior was demonstrated earlier here in studies on quartz (Fig. 23) and limestone (Figs. 22 and 26), and approximately in the study of small particles of alumina (Fig. 16). A clear demonstration can be observed in the work of [Bertrand *et al* \(1988\)](#) on medium-scale refractory particles of alumina. [Figure 33](#) shows edf $Pr(\sigma)$ plots, constructed from the published data using the analysis described above, of four sizes of alumina particles from two sets termed fused and tabular. The symbols in Fig. 33 represent individual failure measurements. The strength distributions exhibit typical particle characteristics of linear trends at small strengths perturbed by short curved tails at large strengths. The distributions in both sets are characterized by invariant thresholds and narrower distributions as the particle size was increased, indicative of stochastic size effects. The lines in Fig. 33 represent best fits by two methods. In the first, Eq. (14) was best fit setting $a_1 = b = 0$ as above to the 2.0 mm and 2.4 mm data for the fused and tabular materials, respectively, providing bases $H_1(\sigma)$ for each material. In the second, Eq. (11) was best fit to the remaining data, treating relative particle size, k_2/k_1 , as a fitting parameter to determine the appropriate $H_2(\sigma)$. It is clear that the data from different sized particles are well described by stochastic size effects acting on a single underlying flaw population. As discussed, although the flaw populations for different materials are not directly accessible or required in this assessment, setting $k_1 = 1$ shows that both populations resemble the Quiou sand population of Fig. 26.

FIG. 33. Strength behavior of refractory alumina particles. *Bertrand et al. (1988)* $D = (3.2, 2.6, 2.0, \text{ and } 1.2)$ mm (fused) and $(3.8, 2.4, 2.0, \text{ and } 1.2)$ mm (tabular), all size uncertainties ± 0.1 mm, $N_{\text{tot}} = 370$.

B. Iron ore

Iron ore is frequently formed into pellets or particles to facilitate air flow through the packed ore in blast furnaces for steel production. The particles also facilitate ore handling and transport. The particles are formed by high-temperature thermal processing and contain about 70 % iron oxide by relative volume, with the remainder other oxides and limestone and clay as flux and binding agents. The nearly spherical particles are typically > 10 mm in size and hence are regarded here as large. In order to develop and refine models for iron ore particle failure during handling and transport, [Gustaffsson *et al.* \(2013a\)](#) used a conventional platen apparatus to measure the strength distribution of a sample of commercial (Swedish) iron ore particles. [Tavares *et al.* \(2018\)](#) used a platen apparatus and impact testing to measure the specific failure energy of a set of four sizes of commercial (Brazilian) iron ore particles. Similar measurements were performed by [Cavalcanti and Tavares \(2018\)](#) using a platen apparatus and by [Gustafsson *et al.* \(2017\)](#) using a split Hopkinson bar impact apparatus, the latter as part of a larger program measuring the properties of ensembles of iron ore particles under shear and confined compression ([Gustafsson *et al.*, 2009, 2013bc](#)).

Figure 34 shows edf $Pr(\sigma)$ plots, constructed from the published data using the analysis described above, of iron ore particles from (a) the work of [Gustaffsson *et al.* \(2013a\)](#) and (b) a set for four sizes of iron ore particles from the work of [Tavares *et al.* \(2018\)](#). The symbols in Fig. 34 represent individual failure measurements; the strengths are comparable. The strength distribution in Fig. 34(a) exhibits typical particle characteristics of a linear trend at small strengths perturbed by a short curved tail at large strengths. The set of strength distributions in Fig. 34(b) exhibit bi-linear trends at small strengths perturbed by short curved tails at large strengths. The distributions in this set are characterized by an invariant threshold and narrower distributions as the particle size was increased, indicative of stochastic size effects. The lines in Fig. 34 represent best fits by two methods similar to that above. In the first, Eq. (14) was best fit unconstrained to the 14 mm data, providing a bi-linear basis $H_1(\sigma)$. In the second, Eq. (11) was best fit to the remaining data, treating relative particle size, k_2/k_1 , as a fitting parameter. It is clear that the data from different sized particles are relatively well described by stochastic size effects acting on a single underlying flaw population. Although not required for analysis, the flaw population here resembled in shape those of the earlier SiC and rutile materials of Fig. 15.

FIG. 34. Strength behavior of iron ore particles. (a) [Gustafsson *et al.* \(2013a\)](#) $D = (11.02 \pm 0.66)$ mm, $N = 47$. (b) [Tavares *et al.* \(2018\)](#) $D = (9$ to $12.5, 12.5$ to $14, 14$ to $16,$ and 16 to $19)$ mm, $N_{\text{tot}} = 474$.

C. Glass

Glass is the stereotypical brittle material and has extensive commercial use in sheet and moulded forms for architectural and domestic uses. Glass particles are also used commercially in many of the applications noted above, including grinding, proppant beds, structural reinforcement in composites, and as catalytic and biological agents. As a consequence, the strength of glass particles was measured in early work by Kschinka *et al.* (1986) using a conventional platen apparatus and more recently by Huang *et al.* (2014) and Shan *et al.* (2018) using a conventional platen apparatus and a split Hopkinson bar impact apparatus. Many intermediate works have examined the failure mechanisms of glass particles, aided by glass transparency (Shipway and Hutchings, 1993; Tavares and King, 1998; Gorham and Salman, 2005; Aman *et al.*, 2010; Rozenblat *et al.*, 2011; Paul *et al.*, 2015; Parab *et al.*, 2017; Pejchal *et al.* 2017). Figure 35 shows edf $Pr(\sigma)$ plots, constructed from the published data using the analysis described above, of sets of glass particles of various sizes from the strength measurement works. The symbols in Fig. 35 represent individual failure measurements; those in Fig. 35(a) are for 2.41 mm size particles. The lines in Fig. 35(a) represent responses described by best fit Weibull description parameters provided by Kschinka *et al.* for 0.51 mm (strongest) to 3.68 mm (weakest) particle sizes over the domains of the reported numbers of particles. As for the majority of the limestone, quartz, rock, and alumina particles described above, the strength distributions reported by Huang *et al.* and Shan *et al.*, Figs. 32(b) and (c), exhibit typical particle characteristics: near linear or weak bi-linear trends at small strengths perturbed by a short curved tails at large strengths and decreasing thresholds and narrower distributions as the particle size was increased, all indicative of deterministic size effects. Also, in common with the limestone and quartz described above (Figs. 22, 23), there was a clear trend between all three studies of decreasing strength sets as the ensemble of particle sizes increased. Hence, the results of Kschinka *et al.* appear quite distinctive. The data appear to be described by an invariant threshold, suggesting a stochastic size effect, in contrast to the later, clearly deterministic, results. The data are reported as sigmoidal, also in contrast to the later, predominantly concave, results, including the failure energy and force observations of Aman *et al.* (2010) and the specific failure energy observations of Rozenblat *et al.* (2011). However, contrarily, Portnikov *et al.* (2013) have reported failure forces for glass spheres of comparable magnitude to those in Kschinka *et al.* that also exhibited sigmoidal distributions characteristics. Sigmoidal

characteristics in glass particle impact velocities have also been observed by [Salman *et al.* \(2002\)](#). Hence, although glass particle failure mechanisms seem well understood, quantitative assessment of failure distributions is ambiguous.

FIG. 35. Strength behavior of glass particles. (a) [Kschinka *et al.* \(1986\)](#) $D = (0.51, 0.65, 0.91, 1.08, 1.27, 1.56, 2.03, 2.41, 3.05, 3.68)$ mm, all uncertainties ± 0.1 mm, $N_{\text{tot}} = 507$. (b) [Huang *et al.* \(2014\)](#) $D = (4.36 \pm 0.08, 8.02 \pm 0.19, 15.77 \pm 0.19, 19.78 \pm 0.15, \text{ and } 24.70 \pm 0.22)$ mm, $N_{\text{tot}} = 169$. (c) [Shan *et al.* \(2018\)](#) $D = (7.71 \pm 0.14, 11.90 \pm 0.1, 17.88 \pm 0.15, \text{ and } 24.87 \pm 0.11)$ mm, $N_{\text{tot}} = 74$.

D. Cement

Concrete components are usually composites, consisting of a cement matrix containing rock and gravel particles (“aggregate”) and metal reinforcing bars (“rebar”). Cement can be used on its own for non-structural applications, but is usually the binder for much stronger, load-bearing composites. Cement is formed by mixing limestone and calcium aluminosilicate minerals and clays and heating the mixture to react and sinter the materials to form cement clinkers, cement particles in the 1 mm to 10 mm size range. Clinkers facilitate handling, transport, and storage of cement, but must be ground into powder for mixing and reaction with water (and more lime) for use in concrete. Hence the strength of cement clinkers is critical to the raw material pre-concrete stages, to avoid material loss by the generation of “fines” and early hydrolysis, and in the concrete production stage, to minimize the energy required for material grinding. The production of cement is a major carbon dioxide emitter and thus optimizing clinker mechanical performance can contribute to reductions in emissions and energy use. Figure 36 shows edf $Pr(\sigma)$ plots, constructed from the published data using the analysis described above, of sets of cement particles of various sizes from the works of May (1974), as cited in Jansen and Stoyan (2000), and Tavares and Cerqueria (2006). The symbols in Fig. 36 represent individual failure measurements; the strengths are significantly greater (tens of megapascals) than those reported for clinkers by Vallet and Charmet (1995) (a few megapascals or less) and discussed earlier (Fig. 3). In both studies in Fig. 36, the strength distributions exhibited decreased strengths, narrower strength distributions, and decreased, very small, thresholds, as particle size increased, characteristic of the deterministic size effects observed in many of the studies above. However, perhaps the most distinctive feature of the data of Fig. 36, not in common with the studies above, is that the strength distribution behavior for all particle sizes in both studies is near linear. The linearity is much more pronounced than that exhibited by the natural particles of rocks and ores of Figs. 19 and 28 and the railway ballasts of Fig. 27, and closely similar to the engineered particles of the bauxite pellets of Fig. 31 and the iron ore pellets of Fig. 34. A common cause for the near-linear strength distribution behavior for these cement clinkers, bauxite proppants, and iron ore pellets may be found in that all three sets of material particles were formed by aggregation and heat treatment of smaller substituents to generate final porous particles. This is not true of the dense rocks mentioned above, with the

implication that porous particles (and perhaps porous macroscopic materials, *cf* Figs. 4 and 5) exhibit distinctive strength behavior as a consequence of distinctive underlying flaw populations.

Inspection of Fig. 7 suggests that near-linear strength distribution responses can be interpreted as the small strength cdf domains of a population, Figs. 7(d), (e), and especially (j). These domains arise, reciprocally, Eq. 5, from the large flaw domains of the population pdf curves, which are characterized in Fig. 7 by heavy tail behavior, most apparent as such in Fig. 7(i) conjugate to Fig. 7(j). Hence, to first approximation, particle strengths that are characterized by linear distribution behavior are controlled by flaw populations that decreases in probability density from small to large flaws over the domain of flaw sizes with non-zero values. The absence of perturbation from such a linear strength distribution response by a short, curved tail at large strengths, Fig. 36, so distinctive in many of the particle studies examined here, suggests such flaw populations may not clearly exhibit the modal maximum at an asymmetric value within the domain, so evident in Figs. 7(g) and (i). Application of Eqs. 2 through 9 in reverse analysis, using a simple linear dependence for $H(\sigma) \sim \sigma$ to describe Fig. 36, yields a deconvoluted flaw population varying approximately as $f(c) \sim c^{-1.5}$. This dependence is stronger than the inverse linear c^{-1} dependence characteristic of so many particle systems (*e.g.*, Figs. 14, 18, 24, 25, 29) but not as strong as the exponential $\exp(-c)$ dependence characteristic of macroscopic specimens (Fig. 14). These observations suggest that porosity may weaken the localization of failure in some particle systems, leading to a “lightening” of the heavy tail. Cements (Fig. 36) provide a clear example.

FIG. 36. Strength behavior of cement particles. (a) [May \(1974\)](#) as cited in [Jansen and Stoyan \(2000\)](#) $D = (4, 5, 6.3, 10, 12, 16, 18, \text{ and } 20)$ mm, $N_{\text{tot}} = 103$. (b) [Tavares and Cerqueira \(2006\)](#) $D = (0.5 \text{ to } 0.7 \text{ and } 8 \text{ to } 9.5)$ mm, $N_{\text{tot}} = 186$.

E. Catalysts

In many industrial chemical engineering processes, reactant gases or liquids are passed over a surface that catalyzes a chemical reaction, such that the reacted fluid product contains new chemical species or has had unwanted species removed. The catalytic surface is often formed by the interior and exterior surfaces of medium to large particles containing small-scale porosity and packed into an array or “bed”, either fixed or mobile (“fluidized”), through which the reactants are passed, and from which the products are collected. Mechanical integrity of such catalyst particles is critical, particularly in fixed bed reactors, as broken or crushed particles can generate “fines,” impeding flow through the particle bed and reducing reactor performance (similar concerns to those regarding air flow through beds of iron ore pellets in blast furnaces, see above). Fracture of catalyst particles may also reduce their catalytic ability. As a consequence, several measurements of the crushing strengths of catalyst particles, porous alumina and zeolite, were performed using a conventional platen apparatus by [Li *et al.* \(1999, 2000\)](#) and [Subero-Couroyer *et al.* \(2003\)](#). [Figure 37](#) shows edf $Pr(\sigma)$ plots, constructed from the published data using the analysis described above, of catalyst particles from these works. The relative porosity of the particles was approximately 40 % by volume. The symbols in Fig. 37 represent individual failure measurements; the strengths are very small (a few megapascals), comparable to the some of the earlier limestone and sand agglomerate observations (Fig. 3). [Antonyuk *et al.* \(2005\)](#) and [Russell *et al.* \(2014\)](#) reported failure energy values equivalent to strength values of approximately 12 MPa to 25 MPa for zeolite catalyst particles tested using conventional platens. [Antonyuk *et al.* \(2005\)](#) and [Müller *et al.* \(2013\)](#) similarly reported values of approximately 45 MPa for alumina catalyst particles. These values are much less than the large strengths, approximately 100 MPa, comparable to dense ceramics, reported by [Samimi *et al.* \(2015\)](#) and [Fedorov and Gulyaeva \(2019\)](#) for sintered alumina catalyst materials tested using conventional platen apparatus. In the studies of Li *et al.*, Figs. 37(a) and (b), the strength distributions are predominantly concave, although exhibiting sigmoidal tendencies in the very small bi-linear sections at small strengths. The study of Subero-Couroyer *et al.*, Fig. 37(c), exhibits a near ideal sigmoidal response, with clear regions of near zero derivative at small and large strengths. In all cases, however, the catalyst behavior displays the clear particle characteristic of a very broad strength distribution, maximum/minimum strength ratios, σ_N/σ_1 , of 5 to 10 are observed in Fig. 37, clearly distinguished from the macroscopic specimen responses in Figs. 4 and

5, in which ratios of two were observed. The catalyst data of Fig. 37 reinforce the idea suggested in the above discussion of cement particles and supported by the observations of bauxite and iron ore particles, that porosity may weaken the localization of failure in agglomerate particles and thus weaken the direct assessment of the flaw population by particle strength tests. Physically, this could be caused by the region of maximum stress expanded beyond the $D/2$ range suggested by **HO**. Porosity weakens the continuum approximation and leads to local regions of enhanced stress within a particle. Mathematically, this is represented by implementation of a true extreme value effect, and $k > 1$ in Eq. 9. The results of porous particles in Figs. 33, 34, and 36, are consistent with such an idea. The experiments of [Wollborn *et al.* \(2017\)](#) on porous agglomerates suggest that the factor of 0.9 in the **HO** formulation is still applicable in characterizing the average magnitude of the stress.

FIG. 37. Strength behavior of catalyst particles. (a) and (b) *Li et al. (1999, 2000)* $D = (4.43 \pm 0.14, 5.75 \pm 0.17, 6.02 \pm 0.14, 4.5 \text{ to } 6.5, \text{ and } 5.5 \text{ to } 6.5) \text{ mm}$, $N_{\text{tot}} = 352$. (c) *Subero-Couroyer et al. (2003)*, $D = (1.7 \text{ to } 2.0) \text{ mm}$, $N = 109$.

F. Foods and Ice

The application of excessive bite force through the jaw to strong (or “hard” or “tough”) particles of foods can lead to chipping of teeth. Such chipping and fracture is of interest to dentists and zoologists to explain current-day human and animal behavior and to anthropologists and paleontologists to explain and reconstruct previous behavior. In order to infer the diets of living and fossil mammals and hominids, [Constantino *et al.* \(2010\)](#) and [Lee *et al.* \(2011\)](#) performed experiments and developed fracture mechanics models to analyze cracks in teeth. Amongst the many conclusions was that some species (*e.g.*, orangutans) frequently eat “fallback” foods, not part of their regular diet, in the form of large, hard particles (*e.g.*, seeds) leading to tooth fracture and some species (*e.g.*, gorillas) rarely eat such foods and rarely exhibit tooth fracture or chipping. In addition, models of tooth fracture suggested that humans should exhibit smaller resistance to tooth cracking relative to other mammals and hominids in terms of critical bite forces. The focus of [Constantino *et al.*](#) and [Lee *et al.*](#) was on teeth. Here the focus is on the food (or other) particles that humans might eat and examines the strength distributions of such particles in the context of tooth fracture.

Figure 38 shows edf $Pr(\sigma)$ plots, constructed from the published data using the analysis described above, of food particles from the works of [McDowell and Humphreys \(2002\)](#) (corn flakes, rice krispies, and pasta), [Pitchumani *et al.* \(2004\)](#) (cellulose), [Singh *et al.* \(2016\)](#) (mustard seeds, peppercorns, unrefined sugar, cake decorations), and [Stefanou and Sulem \(2016\)](#) (rock sugar), all tested using conventional platen apparatus. The data in Fig. 38 have been divided into three groups: (a) porous particles formed from aqueous mixtures containing smaller sub-particles of corn, rice, or wheat and then dried (not dissimilar to the bauxite or iron ore particles above); (b) nearly fully dense particles formed by plants; and (c) dense, crystal-based particles condensed out of sugar solution or sugar-coated particles. There is a clear difference in strength between the food particles formed from sub-particles (a), about one megapascal, and the food particles formed as seeds or crystallized from solution (b) and (c), about 10 megapascals. In all cases the strength distributions are predominantly concave, although exhibiting some sigmoidal tendencies through the small bi-linear sections at small strengths, particularly in Fig. 38(b). In most cases the data display the clear particle characteristic of a very broad strength distribution, maximum/minimum

strength ratios $\sigma_N/\sigma_1 > 10$ are observed, particularly in Figs. 38(a) and (c). Similar observations for sugar particles were made by [Rozenblat *et al.* \(2011\)](#).

Using the observations of Constantino *et al.* and Lee *et al.* that human bite forces necessary for tooth cracking are about 500 N, the upper bound strength data of Fig. 38 and Eq. 1 suggest that a 17 mm cornflake, an 8 mm peppercorn, or a 4 mm chunk of rock sugar could lead to a cracked tooth. The first particle is unlikely to be encountered, but the second and third are very common, although the broad domain of strengths suggests that fracture conditions are unlikely to be frequent for these food particles. Conversely, the significantly stronger particles of sand, about 100 megapascals (Figs. 22, 23, 26) suggest that accidental biting of “grit” particles could easily lead to tooth fracture in both humans and other animals. Figure 6(a) shows that the salt particles measured by [Rozenblat *et al.* \(2011\)](#) are comparable to the sugar particles of Fig. 38(c) and could thus also lead to dietary tooth fracture. Similar salt particle results were obtained by [Aman *et al.* \(2010\)](#) and [Portnikov *et al.* \(2013\)](#).

Figure 39 shows edf $Pr(\sigma)$ plots, constructed from the published data using the analysis described above, of polycrystalline ice particles or blocks from the work of [Kuehn *et al.* \(1993\)](#) tested using a conventional, but large, platen apparatus. There are two distinctive features in the strength distributions of Fig. 39: the first is that the distributions for all sizes are nearly linear; the second is that there is a very small dependence of the strength distribution on particle size, a small weakening for larger blocks is observed. The implications from the above discussion regarding linear strength distributions for cement is that the flaw population underlying the strengths of Fig. 39 is dominated by a decreasing non-zero density function almost independent of particle size. Grain boundaries could well play the role of porosity in this case. The implication from the above discussion and calculations regarding strength distributions of food particles is that it is unlikely that tooth fracture could result from biting an ice block.

FIG. 38. Strength behavior of food particles. (a) McDowell and Humphreys (2002) (corn flakes, rice krispies, and pasta), (irregular, 5 to 20) mm, $N_{\text{tot}} = 87$. (b) and (c) Pitchumani *et al.* (2004) (cellulose) (0.75 to 1.2) mm, $N = 64$, Singh *et al.* (2016) (mustard seeds, peppercorns, unrefined sugar, cake decorations) (1.6 to 2.6, 3.4 to 5.4, 0.8 to 2.2, and 1.2 to 2.0, respectively) mm, $N_{\text{tot}} = 246$, and Stefanou and Sulem (2016) (rock sugar) (6.3 to 8.0) mm, $N = 71$.

FIG. 39. Strength behavior of ice blocks. *Kuehn et al. (1993)* Edge lengths, $D = (10 \text{ to } 150) \text{ mm}$, $N_{\text{tot}} = 111$

G. Silicon- and carbon-based

Final examples of engineered particles are shown in Fig. 40, illustrating the diversity and contrasts of modern-day particles. Edf $Pr(\sigma)$ plots, constructed from the published data using the analysis described above, are shown of (a) Si_3N_4 particles from the work of Wereszczak *et al.* (2007) and (b) graphene-based particles from the work of Rozenblat *et al.* (2011), both obtained using a conventional platen apparatus. The strength distributions of Fig. 40(a), represent the behavior of hot-pressed, dense, bearing grade polycrystalline Si_3N_4 machined into “C-sphere” shaped specimens. In these specimens, a notch is milled in one side of a particle such that the exterior surface of the resulting C is placed in tension when the particle is loaded in diametral compression. As such, these “particle” specimens are more closely related to “large” bending specimens than true particles. The specimens are somewhat similar to the diametrically-loaded C-ring, specimens investigated by Shelleman *et al.* (1991) as part of a study of silicon carbide including O-ring, bending, and pressurized tube specimens, and by de With (1984) on diametrically-loaded alumina O-ring specimens (that exhibited a clear size effect). The strength distributions here of the three different commercial grades of Si_3N_4 tested in the C configuration reflect the “large” geometry and closely resemble the bending specimen strength data of Fig. 3: The data are approximately sigmoidal and the widths of the strength distributions in terms of the σ_N/σ_1 ratio are about factors of two. The strengths of the materials are about 1 GPa, reflecting the strong covalent bonding and hence large fracture resistance of Si_3N_4 , and the small flaws on the highly polished bearing particle surfaces. In contrast, the strength distribution of Fig. 40(b) represents the behavior of graphene nanoplatelet (GNP) particles. The distribution is consistent with the extensive particle observations above: predominantly concave with an extended tail at large strength and a width of the strength distribution in terms of the σ_N/σ_1 ratio of about a factor of four. The distribution is similar in shape to that reported for failure load of GNP particles by Liburkin *et al.* (2015). The strengths of the materials are about 10 MPa, reflecting the weak van der Waals bonding and hence small fracture resistance of the graphene ensemble.

FIG. 40. Strength behavior of technologically-advanced C- and Si-based particles. (a) Si_3N_4 particles from the work of [Wereszczak et al. \(2007\)](#) 12.7 mm, $N_{tot} = 97$. (b) Graphene nano platelet (GNP)-based particles from the work of [Rozenblat et al. \(2011\)](#) $D = (2.36 \text{ to } 3.35) \text{ mm}$, $N = 56$.

VIII. OVERALL PARTICLE STRENGTH TRENDS

One of the most important questions introduced in this review is “What is the effect of size on particle strength”? That question is addressed in this section by combining the complete set of strength data presented in five previous sections (background, and small, medium, large, and engineered particles) and considering overall trends in various aspects of particle strength behavior. This section is divided as previously. The first sub-section examines trends in strength behavior across the complete domain of materials reviewed, making no assumptions regarding the forms of strength distributions or relations between strengths for particles of individual materials. The second and third sub-sections examine trends in flaw behavior and re-emphasize a major point in this review: material flaw populations are the fundamental entities of failure, underlying observed particle strength distributions. Hence, these two sub-sections examine two trends in flaw behavior, recognizing that particle size influences strengths by sampling flaws from the population in two predominant modes. In the first mode, particle size sets the flaw population from which strength-controlling flaws are sampled, typically leading to increased *size* of flaws as particle size increases. This is deterministic behavior, typically leading to decreasing threshold strength, and thus increasing maximum flaw size, with increasing particle size This is the subject of the second sub-section. In the second mode, flaw population is invariant and particle size sets the probability with which strength-controlling flaws are sampled through an increased *number* of flaws as particle size increases. This is stochastic behavior, leading to invariant threshold strength and decreasing strength distribution width with increasing particle size This is the subject of the third sub-section. The data are presented in unbiased form as median and range values, the 50th percentile and the span of (0 to 100) percentiles, respectively, of experimental observations.

A. Materials

Figure 41 shows a plot in logarithmic coordinates of particle strength vs particle diameter from approximately 100 data sets drawn from the previous sections and a few additional selected publications. (For clarity, a small number of data sets from the previous sections and elsewhere, *e.g.*, (Tavares, 2004), were omitted as overlapping those in Fig. 41.) The diversity of particle behavior is demonstrated by the fact that the diameter range extends a factor of 10^5 , centered about 1 mm, and the strength range extends a factor of 10^4 , centered about 10 MPa. The open, grayed,

symbols in Fig. 41 represent a combination of strength measurements of individual particles from Fig. 3, including agglomerates (exhibiting smaller strengths) and monoliths (exhibiting larger strengths); different open symbols represent different materials. The bars and solid symbols in Fig. 41 represent the diameter domains, strength ranges, and appropriate median values of strength measurements of the particle sets detailed in sections IV, V, VI, and VII, including predominantly monolithic materials (*e.g.*, oxides, carbides, carbonates). The solid lines in Fig. 41 are empirical of slope $-1/2$.

Perhaps the most striking feature of Fig. 41 is that the median strength values of the monolithic particles, encompassing a diversity of material types (*e.g.*, rocks, salt, glass, cement, ceramics, sand), exhibit a clear $D^{-1/2}$ trend. The interpretation of this behavior can be made clear by re-writing Eq. (5) as

$$\sigma = B(D/c)^{1/2}D^{-1/2} = \bar{B}D^{-1/2}, \quad (17)$$

where \bar{B} represents an averaged value of the combination of material toughness and particle size/crack size ratio. Fig. 41 suggests that such a \bar{B} value exists and is bounded empirically by $\bar{B} = 200 \text{ MPa mm}^{1/2}$, the upper line in Fig. 41, and $\bar{B} = 25 \text{ MPa mm}^{1/2}$, the lower line, noting that $1 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2} \approx 31 \text{ MPa mm}^{1/2}$. The upper bound of \bar{B} and an upper estimate of $B = 1 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$ for monolithic particles provide an estimate of crack size in terms of particle size from Eq. 17 as $c \approx 0.03D$. Similarly, the lower bound of \bar{B} and a lower estimate of $B = 0.3 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$ provides $c \approx 0.14D$. The implication is that to first order the strength of “hard” particles is a decreasing function of particle diameter given by Eq. (17), applicable from $1 \mu\text{m}$ particles to 100 mm particles with $\bar{B} \approx 70 \text{ MPa mm}^{1/2}$. An example is starting with sand, *e.g.*, from Fig. 3(e), and other mineral particles less than 1 mm in scale and moving to the right diagonally within the band across the graph to rock particles greater than 10 mm in scale, *e.g.*, from Fig. 27. If second order effects are considered, variation greater or smaller by a factor of three in \bar{B} includes most hard particles, with the implication that particles formed from less tough materials contain strength-controlling cracks that are larger relative to particle size. An example here is starting with alumina abrasives about 1 mm in scale at the upper bound, *e.g.*, from Fig. 30, and moving vertically down the graph within the band to cement clinkers of the same scale at the lower bound, *e.g.*, from Fig. 36. (The estimates here are internally self-consistent in that $c < 0.5D$, the size of the uniform tension zone calculated by [Hiramatsu and Oka \(1966\)](#) and used to determine the strengths initially.)

A second clear feature of Fig. 41 is that the agglomerate particle systems are significantly weaker, about 0.1 MPa strengths, and distinct from the band of monolithic materials. The implication is that in comparison with the monolithic materials, bonding within the agglomerates is very weak, probably dominated by hydrogen bonds or van der Waals bonding remnant from the rotary milling or drying stages of fabrication (Knoop *et al.*, 2016; Wollborn *et al.*, 2017), although Capes (1971) claims bonding by NaCl “bridges.” Other materials also appear separate from the main band of monolithic materials, including the early observations of cement clinkers, open symbols about 1 MPa, and the observations of coal, open symbols about 10 MPa, on the edge of the band. An interpretation here is that the weak cement clinkers contained significant porosity, an interpretation supported by the observation that measurements on green bauxite pellets, porous catalysts, and porous foods, all solid symbols, Figs. 31(a), 37, and 38, appear in this band. An interpretation of the coal observations is that the bonding was probably dominated by van der Waals’ bonds between sub-particles of C-rich material, an interpretation supported by the observation that measurements on the GNP particles, Fig. 40(b), appear in this range.

A third feature of Fig. 41 is that, as noted throughout, the ranges of strengths are quite large for most measurements. The ranges are about a factor of 10 or more, independent of particle material or diameter, in spite of the fact that the sorted or sieved domains of particle sizes in most cases are quite small (*e.g.*, the observations at about 0.04 mm). The implication here is that large strength dispersion is an inherent feature of particle behavior, reflecting a large dispersion of strength-controlling flaw sizes, and hence a broad sampling of underlying flaw populations with large relative dispersions. A further implication, combined with the analysis of section III, is that a diversity of responses is *expected* for experimental measurements of strength dependence on particle size. The median value data of Fig. 41, if interpreted as slopes within the drawn band, give $\sigma \sim D^{-0.5 \pm 0.2}$. However, the total range data of Fig. 41, extending beyond the band, give $\sigma \sim D^{-0.5 \pm 0.5}$, more in accord with this expected diversity, and consistent with Fig. 3 and the previous cited estimates based on individual particle or mean value measurements (Kapur and Furstenu, 1967), (Capes, 1971), (Vallet and Charmet, 1995), (McDowell and Amon, 2000), (Nakata *et al.*, 2001b), (Lobo-Guerrero *et al.*, 2006b), (Wang *et al.*, 2015), and (Xu *et al.*, 2016).

An original goal of this work would thus appear to be fulfilled in that the small size of particles does enable direct assessment of flaw populations through strength measurement. Figure 41 implies that a qualitative aspect of such populations is nearly universal in that they are widely

dispersed. The following two sub-sections address quantitative aspects of flaw populations in particles.

FIG. 41. Plot of strength σ vs diameter D for all particle systems reviewed here; open symbols indicate individual measurements, solid symbols indicate median values of distributions, solid lines indicate $D^{-1/2}$ behavior. There is a clear difference in strength between dense, monolithic particles and porous, agglomerate particles.

B. Deterministic systems

The simplest distinction within particle flaw populations is between the group of populations that depend on particle size and the group that do not. The former group exhibits deterministic behavior, as particle size determines the flaw population, and it is intuitive that the largest flaw in a deterministic population should increase in size with particle size (and, perhaps, so should the smallest flaws (Epstein, 1948b), but as discussed in the Introduction, these are irrelevant in strength considerations). The implication is that threshold strengths, the smallest strengths in a set of distributions, should thus decrease with increasing particle size in deterministic systems. Such decreases were taken here as indicative of deterministic systems (*e.g.*, Fig. 28) and the question thus arises “How does the size of the largest flaw scale with particle size in deterministic systems”? In terms of the notation here, the question becomes “what is the $c_{\max}(D)$ relationship”?

For a set of particle sizes, $D_i < D_j < D_k \dots$ in a deterministic system, the separate flaw populations will have maxima given by $c_{\max,i} < c_{\max,j} < c_{\max,k} \dots$, such that $c_{\max,i}$ is the least upper bound of the populations. The strength distributions of particles sampled from this set will thus exhibit conjugate thresholds $\sigma_{\text{th},i} > \sigma_{\text{th},j} > \sigma_{\text{th},k} \dots$, such that $\sigma_{\text{th},i}$ is the greatest lower bound of the distributions. Using these bounds and Eq. (5) gives $c_{\max,j}/c_{\max,i} = (\sigma_{\text{th},i}/\sigma_{\text{th},j})^2$, which may be compared with the ratio D_j/D_i to estimate the required relationship. Figure 42 uses the information in Figs. 6, 16, 22, 23, 27, 28, 30, 35, and 36 from systems judged to be deterministic to plot $c_{\max,j}/c_{\max,i}$ vs D_j/D_i , shown as the solid symbols. Information from selected publications was similarly used to generate the open symbols. Experimental strength ratios were used to determine $c_{\max,j}/c_{\max,i}$ and cited particle size information was used to determine size ratio D_j/D_i and uncertainty. The solid lines in Fig. 42 indicate scaling relationships of $c_{\max,j}/c_{\max,i} = (D_j/D_i)^n$, where $n = 0.5, 1, \text{ or } 2$. Although Fig. 42 makes clear that deterministic flaw population behavior is in accord with intuition—larger particles have populations with additional larger flaws, $c_{\max,j}/c_{\max,i}$ increases with D_j/D_i —there does not appear to be a universal scaling behavior. Nearly all deterministic particle flaw systems are described by the bounds of scaling between $n = 0.5$ and $n = 2$. However, as most variable size particle systems are restricted to $D_j/D_i < 10$, stronger scaling of $n = 1$ to $n = 2$ is more prevalent. Note that $n = 2$ corresponds to linear scaling of threshold with particle size, $\sigma_{\text{th},i}/\sigma_{\text{th},j} = D_j/D_i$, such that threshold variations are anticipated to be sub-linear with particle size (*i.e.*, vary weakly), consistent with the above Figures.

FIG. 42. Plot of maximum flaw size c_{\max} vs diameter D for all deterministic particle systems reviewed here; data referenced to small particle measurements, solid lines indicate ranges of scaling behavior.

C. Stochastic systems

If the population of flaws is invariant and therefore independent of particle size, a set of particles of different sizes containing flaws from such a population exhibits stochastic behavior—particle size determines the number of flaws and thus the probability that a particle will contain a flaw of a given size. In particular, as the population is invariant, the largest flaw sampled is invariant and the threshold strengths, the smallest strengths in a set of distributions, should thus be invariant. Such invariance was taken here as indicative of stochastic systems (*e.g.*, Fig. 30) and the question thus arises “How does the number of flaws scale with particle size in stochastic systems”? In terms of the notation here, the question becomes “what is the $k(D)$ relationship”?

For a set of particle sizes, $D_i < D_j < D_k \dots$ in a stochastic system, the strength distributions will be related by Eq. (11) with $k_i < k_j < k_k \dots$, where k_i is the number of flaws in particle i and only the ratios $1 < k_j/k_i < k_k/k_i \dots$ can be determined from strength tests. **Figure 43** uses the information in Figs. 22, 23, 26, 33, 34, 35, and 36 from systems judged to be stochastic to plot k_j/k_i vs D_j/D_i , shown as the solid symbols for systems discussed in detail above and open symbols otherwise. Fits to experimental strength distributions were used to determine k_j/k_i and cited particle size information was used to determine size ratio D_j/D_i and uncertainty. The solid lines in Fig. 43 indicate scaling relationships of $k_j/k_i = (D_j/D_i)^n$, where $n = 0, 1, 2,$ or 3 . The trivial, although rare, case of $n = 0$, such that $k_j/k_i = 1$, is exhibited by ice, Fig. 39, and perhaps by some of the larger mineral and rock particles, Figs. 26 and 28. Although Fig. 43 makes clear that stochastic flaw population behavior is in accord with intuition—larger particles include more flaws, k_j/k_i increases with D_j/D_i —there does not appear to be a universal scaling behavior. Nearly all stochastic particle flaw systems are described by the bounds of scaling between $n = 1$ and $n = 3$, although, with one notable exception, most observations have not included enough particle sizes or a wide enough range of sizes to arrive at a definitive judgement. The exception is the observations of **Kschinka *et al.* (1986)** on glass spheres, Fig. 35(a), which could not be fully analyzed as the raw data were not published, and which thus appear in Fig. 43 as the open symbols close to the $(D_j/D_i)^3$ line. The data suggest a “volume” scaling, that is the number of flaws scales as the volume of the particle, a finding previously reached by **Kschinka *et al.*** based on a Weibull description of strength

distributions. However, in the absence of the raw data and the existence of more recent observations displaying deterministic behavior (Fig. 35), no conclusion can be drawn.

FIG. 43. Plot of number of flaws k vs diameter D for all stochastic particle systems reviewed here; data referenced to small particle measurements; solid lines indicate ranges of scaling behavior.

IX. DISCUSSION

A. Physical insights

This review has examined, in considerable quantitative detail, experimental strength distributions of particles. Individual particle strengths, σ , have been determined and presented using a single strength formulation (HO) based on the common loading configuration of diametral compression. Groups of strengths have been presented using an unbiased format for the resulting empirical distribution functions (edf)s, $Pr(\sigma)$. The review has been wide-ranging, extending over more than 30 materials systems, including over 180 published strength distributions derived from over 11 400 individual particle strength measurements. The extensive set of strength data has been classified by particle size, extending from micrometers to tens of millimeters, and material, focusing on monolithic, inorganic brittle particles, primarily oxides and carbonates. A key feature of the review has been the inclusion of recent extreme value analyses relating strength distributions and underlying material flaw populations, here in the context of particle behavior, providing an additional, critical, means of classification by stochastic or deterministic extreme value effects.

There are no comparable reviews of this subject. Prior, smaller, reviews have focused on strength measurements of particles in various indirect tensile test geometries and a single material (Darvell, 1990), or on a small number of materials and few direct comparisons (Ryu and Saito, 1991), or on analysis rather than presentation of measurements (Chau *et al.*, 2000). Although it is clear in the earliest particle studies from most groups that strength distributions are recognized as inversely reflecting flaw size distributions, *e.g.*, (Kschinka *et al.*, 1986), (Huang *et al.*, 1993), (Tavares and King, 1998), (McDowell and Amon, 2000), (Salman and Gorham, 2000), (Vogel and Peukert, 2002), there have been no quantitative assessments of flaw size distributions. As noted in Section II, many detailed quantitative analyses have been performed of the elastic stress fields that develop within particles on diametral loading. In addition, similarly detailed analyses have been performed of the stress fields that develop externally at particle-platen contacts on loading. These analyses have been applied in developing triaxial stress-based failure criteria (Gustafsson *et al.*, 2013a) or in determining the conditions for localized plastic deformation (Antonyuk *et al.*, 2005) or fracture (Brzesowsky *et al.*, 2011; Russell *et al.*, 2014). Overall, however, the connection

between the strength distributions and flaw populations has been implicit and qualitative: small flaws generate large strengths.

Here, application of the recent probabilistic analysis to the assembled wide-ranging data set has enabled much greater quantitative insight. Specifically, as reviewed in Section III, the analysis enables flaw distributions and underlying flaw populations to be determined quantitatively from strength distribution measurements, as demonstrated previously on large specimens (Cook and DelRio, 2019ab). Similar determinations of flaw populations from particle strength measurements have been a key part of this review. However, a major innovative feature of the review has been the development of a clear distinction between particle systems that exhibit stochastic size effects and those that exhibit deterministic size effects. The distinction reflects a difference in the dependence on particle size of strength-controlling, extreme, flaws. In both size effects, groups of particles form extreme value flaw distributions selected from an underlying flaw population. In systems exhibiting stochastic size effects, the flaw population is invariant. In systems exhibiting deterministic size effects, the flaw population varies with particle size, typically by including larger flaws in the population as the particle size increases. Strength measurements are a probe of the extreme value flaw distribution: an invariant strength threshold is indicative of a stochastic size effect; a strength threshold decreasing with increasing particle size is indicative of a deterministic size effect. About a quarter of the particle systems examined here exhibited stochastic size effects, typified by the measurements of McDowell and Amon (2000) on Quiou sand (Fig. 26). About half the particle systems examined here exhibited deterministic size effects, typified by the measurements of Tavares and Das Neves (2008) on quarry rock (Fig. 28). Very few of the systems examined here included particles small enough such that stochastic and deterministic effects converged at the limit of one flaw/particle. In these systems, extreme value effects are absent, and the material flaw population is probed directly, typified by the measurements of Ribas *et al.* (2014) on SiC and Herre *et al.* (2017) on TiO₂ (Fig. 17).

An additional, quantitative, and pervasive observation, independent of particle material and size effects, is that the vast majority of particle strength distributions are concave, exemplified in Fig. 6. The distributions exhibit linear variations at small strengths adjacent to the threshold before curving to extended tails at large strengths. The majority, more than three quarters, of particle strength distributions presented here were concave. Although variations were observed, particularly the relative domains of the linear and curved segments and the appearance of bi-linear

segments, most distributions could not be described as sigmoidal. This behavior is in clear distinction to that observed for “large” bend, tensile, or compression specimens, Figs. 4 and 5, which exhibit clear sigmoidal behavior. Further, particle strength distributions are broad, typically more than a factor of four, compared with strength distributions of large samples, which exhibit widths of a factor of two. Applying the analyses discussed above to these observations shows that particle flaw populations are typified by heavy tails tending to non-zero values at large flaw sizes, Fig. 13. This behavior is quite distinct from that of large specimens that typically exhibit light tails tending to zero at large flaw sizes, Fig. 12. The difference in shape is made clear in Fig. 14. Heavy tails in flaw distributions, leading to linearity in strength distributions, was observed in all systems: deterministic, *e.g.*, [Verspui *et al.* \(1997\)](#), Fig. 15, stochastic, *e.g.*, [Bertrand *et al.* \(1988\)](#), Fig. 33, and intermediate, *e.g.*, [Wong *et al.*, \(1987\)](#), Fig. 31. The physical implication is that fracture instability events that would be regarded as rare in large specimens, *i.e.*, small strengths arising from large flaws, are frequent in particles, leading to broadened strength distributions.

Independent of distribution shape considerations, strength magnitudes can be assessed in an unbiased manner using the measured medians and ranges (these are better measures of central tendency for wide distributions, as here). These parameters exhibit a clear, perhaps unsurprising, distinction between stronger monolithic particles and weaker agglomerate particles, Fig. 41. In addition, the monolithic particles, nearly all covalently bonded, exhibit a clear decreasing trend with increasing particle size, well approximated by a $D^{-1/2}$ band. Similar decreasing trends had, of course, been observed in single material systems, see description of Fig. 3, but the review here indicates that an overall size effect trend exists. The analysis of Section III suggests that the trend cannot reflect universal size effect behavior in terms of a single exponent (say, -0.5) pertaining to individual particle systems, stochastic or deterministic, and hence Fig. 41 represents particle behavior, not measurement imprecision. Similarly, the observed weakly-increasing trends with particle size, for maximum flaw size in deterministic systems and number of flaws in stochastic systems, Figs. 42 and 43, respectively, probably reflect in part the inherently broad particle flaw size distributions and populations.

B. Distributions

Almost none of the findings detailed above could have been made from the published data. The dominant tendency to publish strength edf data in transformed coordinates—over three quarters of the works cited—significantly obscured strength distribution shapes, magnitudes, and relative behavior, rendering physical insight almost impossible. The historical motivation for this tendency is that transformed coordinates lead to easily-fit straight-line behavior of the data if an assumed linearized analytical form for $Pr(\sigma)$ is followed. In many works however, the transformation was implemented to follow historical precedent, regardless of any fit and little use, if any, was made of the parameters describing the assumed form of $Pr(\sigma)$.

The most common transformation was based on the assumption of a two-parameter stretched exponential function for the extreme value strength distribution. This function is popularized in the Weibull description as $H(\mu) = 1 - \exp(-\mu^m)$, using the notation of Eq. (12) and setting $\sigma_{\min} = 0$, $\sigma_{\max} = \sigma_0$, and $\mu = \sigma/\sigma_0$, to leave two degrees of freedom, m and σ_0 . The analogous assumed form for the strength edf is $Pr(\sigma) = 1 - \exp[-(\sigma/\sigma_0)^m]$. In this form, the assumed edf is sigmoidal and has zero threshold. Inspection of the data in unbiased form in the body of this review show that these assumptions very rarely describe particle strength observations. Hence, the two-parameter Weibull description is usually a very poor fit to most particle data. Linearization into the form $y(x) = ax + b$ is achieved by the transformations $y = \ln[\ln(1/(1 - P))]$ and $x = \ln\sigma$, such that $m = a$ and $\sigma_0 = \exp(b/a)$, and these are the parameters commonly cited. However, the data in transformed coordinates are invariably still clearly concave, as noted in the earlier review of large specimen measurements by [Shih \(1980\)](#), and as may be seen in the historical progression of original particle works cited here, *e.g.*, [Brecker, 1974](#); [Wong et al., 1987](#), [Huang et al., 1995](#); [McDowell, 2002](#); [Wang et al., 2015](#)). Of greatest impediment, however, is that linearizing this assumed form requires multiple, contracting, logarithmic transformations that completely obscure the real shape of edfs, obscure the relative widths of edfs, and most crucially, obscure the relative threshold positions of edfs. Interpretation is often made more difficult by the tendency to implement contracted graph axes, rendering the data almost vertical and falsely enhancing the linearity, *e.g.*, in the strength measurements of ceramic tubes by [Shelleman et al. \(1991\)](#) and of cellulose compacts by [Keleş et al. \(2015\)](#). Less common transformations, largely applied to specific failure energy data of particles, include that based on the normal distribution and error function, $H(\mu) = [1 + \text{erf}(\mu)]/2$, ([King and Bourgeois, 1993](#); [Tavares and King, 1998](#); [Tavares and das Neves, 2008](#)) and a range of other transformations similarly based on assumed sigmoidal

behavior, such as the Gumbel, $H(\mu) = \exp[-\exp(-\mu)]$, logistic, $H(\mu) = 1/[1 + \exp(-\mu)]$, and Gamma distributions (Gustafsson *et al.*, 2013a; Cavalcanti and Tavares, 2018; Tavares *et al.*, 2018). Non-linear perturbations include $\mu \rightarrow \ln\mu$ and $\mu \rightarrow \mu^p$, noting that the last form was used here in Eq. (13) to perturb the incomplete Beta function (Cook and DelRio, 2019ab; Cook *et al.*, 2019; Cook, 2020).

There are three major reasons to believe that emphasis on such functions in describing strength distributions is misplaced. First, empirical. As demonstrated here and elsewhere (Cook and DelRio, 2019ab), the use of unbiased strength edf coordinates provides insights regarding strength distribution shapes and thresholds that are obscured in transformed coordinates. Second, numerical. The application of modern-day desktop computers has rendered the need for linearized $Pr(\sigma)$ forms obsolete; smoothing of experimental strength data is easily accomplished. Third, the fitting of common probability distributions, *e.g.*, Weibull, Gumbel, or normal, to strength measurements suggests a fundamental physical interpretation that is unlikely to be true. As noted throughout this review, the fundamental physical characteristic controlling failure of particles is the flaw population. Stochastic and deterministic size effects lead to ensembles of flaws in individual particles. Extreme value effects lead to distributions of maximally potent flaws in groups of particles. Strength measurements are simply probes of these flaws. Given the non-linear relationship between strength and flaw size (Eq. 5) and the non-linear nature of extreme-value size effects (Eq. 9), it is extremely unlikely that strength distributions are simple or easily interpretable. The complexities are outlined in Figs. 7 and 8 and in consideration of a simple quadratic flaw population in Cook and DelRio (2019a).

As noted in the Introduction, distribution parameters for strength and strength-related properties (*e.g.*, specific failure energy, King and Bourgeois, 1993, failure velocity, Salman *et al.*, 2002) are of great importance for particle applications in engineering, *e.g.*, estimation of energy needs in mining or concrete manufacture (Tavares, 2004; Tromans, 2008; Schneider *et al.*, 2011). Hence, there is a practical need for succinct description of behavior, *e.g.*, by the normal distribution. However, the observations reviewed here suggest that even strength distributions of particles, which might be physically small enough and tested in large-enough numbers, very rarely provide direct insight into flaw populations by evading extreme value considerations (see Section IV). Hence, interpreting a particular functional form for a strength distribution in physical terms, *e.g.*, (Fischer *et al.*, 2002; Lu *et al.*, 2002; R'Mili *et al.*, 2012; Wiess *et al.*, 2014; Taloni *et al.*,

2018) is likely to be inconclusive. Of potentially greater importance is that interpretation of the Weibull form is likely to be misleading. As emphasized here and earlier, in works considering ceramics (Shih, 1980), hazard (Todinov, 2010), fibers (Zok, 2017), and MEMS (Cook and DelRio, 2019a), the concept of flaw independence, equivalent to weakest-link behavior, is completely separate from any consideration of any form of the flaw population. Historically, however, the two concepts have become conflated, as can be observed in many of the works cited here, such that weakest-link behavior is now often regarded as the basis of Weibull “theory”, e.g., Brzesowksy *et al.* (2011). As a consequence, observations of apparent Weibull curves using transformed coordinates are taken as implying underlying weakest link behavior, when in fact no such implication can be drawn. The engineering and physics consequences are that stochastic size effect scaling based on a light-tailed flaw population are erroneously assumed. The review here shows that both assumptions for particles are likely to be in error. Reservations regarding the applicability of the Weibull description are not new: as noted by Gorksi (1968) regarding reliability, “nobody has been able to present a sufficient argument for the Weibull case.”

C. Related materials and behavior

An important class of particles are pharmaceutical tablets, usually formed by die compaction of powders into disc-shaped form. In addition to an active pharmaceutical ingredient (API), the powders usually contain additives to aid in compaction, binding, and API release. A key element in tablet manufacturing is to optimize binding in compaction so that tablets are strong enough for storage and transport but not so strong that API release is inhibited. The variation of tablet strength with compaction pressure and subsequent environmental exposure is thus a focus of pharmaceutical manufacturing. Tablet strength has usually been measured by diametral compression (Fig. 1) of 2-D, near cylindrical, tablets (particles) in the classic “Brazilian” thin disc geometry. Major contributions to tablet strength measurement have been made by Newton, Stanley, and colleagues from the 1970s onwards.

The early tablet strength tests of Fell and Newton (1970) established the major features of such measurements. Fell and Newton compacted various grades of lactose powders, composed of about 30 μm (sub-)particles, in $D = 12.7$ mm flat-faced cylindrical dies with pressures up to 400 MPa to yield thin disc tablets about 3 mm thick. Diametral compression of the discs led to tensile fracture

and failure at loads of about (100 to 300) N. Application of the conventional 2-D stress formula, $\sigma = 2L_{\max}/\pi Dt$ (Jaeger, 1967), where t is the thickness, indicated strengths of about 6 MPa. Greater compaction pressures led to greater fracture strengths. Padded platens led to both greater loads and load variability at failure, perhaps for the same reasons as the observations of Brecker (1974) on alumina particles with ground flats (see section V. A).

In the intervening years since Fell and Newton's work, similar observations of failure loads in the range 50 N to 150 N have been made on flat disc tablets formed from (20 to 700) μm powders using (5 to 12.5) mm dies and (8 to 700) MPa compaction pressures. The inferred strengths are of course also similar and include: aspirin (Kennerly *et al.*, 1982), (0.6 to 1.4) MPa; sucrose, (Es-Saheb, 1996), (0.2 to 4) MPa; salt, lactose, sucrose, dicalcium phosphate dihydrate, and cellulose, (Adolfsson *et al.*, 1997) (0.5 to 5) MPa; cellulose, lactose, and commercial tablets (Sonnergaard, 2002), (1 to 4) MPa; salt, sucrose, and paracetamol (Fichtner *et al.*, 2005), (0.1 to 2.5) MPa; cellulose (Keleş *et al.*, 2015), (0.2 to 6) MPa; and lactose-cellulose bilayers (Chang *et al.*, 2017) (0.1 to 1.6) MPa. (some data conversions were required), with greater strengths reflecting greater compaction pressures. Tablet strength testing was greatly extended by Pitt, Newton, and Stanley in the 1980s, through the introduction of a stress formulation for tablets with the common shape of double-convex exteriors. The formulation was demonstrated on wet cast gypsum (plaster) with a strength of about 5.2 MPa and verified by photoelastic experiments by Pitt *et al.* (1988, 1989). Detailed comparisons of flat and double convex tablet strengths were subsequently performed by Es-Saheb (1996), Newton *et al.* (2000a), (0.6 to 2) MPa, and particularly by Shang *et al.* (2013a), (40 to 400) N failure loads. Verifications by finite element analyses include those by Pitt and Heasley (2013) (3 MPa maximum) and Shang *et al.* (2013b). Elongated cellulose tablets, treated as uniaxial beams, exhibited larger strengths, Newton *et al.* (2000b) and Podczeczek *et al.* (2006), (0.2 to 12) MPa, as did biaxially-flexed sorbitol discs (4 to 20) MPa (Podczeczek, 2007). The implication of the uniaxial and biaxial tests, more typical of ceramic "large" specimens (Cook, 2015), is that surface flaws are less potent than bulk flaws in these powder compacts.

A few works considering tablet-like particle strengths have presented edf $Pr(\sigma)$ or related $h(\sigma)$ data, (Kennerly *et al.*, 1982), (Stanley, 2001), (Sonnergaard, 2002), (Keleş *et al.*, 2015). In most cases, the edf responses were approximately linear or slightly sigmoidal, rather than concave, more like the observations on porous bauxite, iron ore, and cement than the observations on the majority of dense particle considered here. The implication, as suggested in section VII. D. on cement is

that porous particles, or tablets, formed from sub-particles, exhibit larger tensile zones relative to particle diameter than do dense particles. The enlarged zone leads to greater sampling of the flaw ensemble within the entire particle and thus greater extreme value effects and more narrow strength distributions: a clear example in porous cellulose compacts is shown by [Keleş *et al.* \(2015\)](#). Independent of edf shape, the characteristic *strengths* of tablets, 1 MPa to 5 MPa, are in the range of most foods, 0.1 MPa to 20 MPa, see Fig. 38, and the failure *loads*, 50 N to 150 N, are less than the 500 N estimated as necessary to cause tooth cracking, see section VII. F. Consistent with the insights into porous particle failure, it is noted that the dense microcrystalline cellulose particles are stronger, 10 MPa to 20 MPa, Fig. 38(b), than the porous cellulose tablets considered above. In all, the strengths of tablets are consistent with other engineering particle measurements and with chewability by humans.

Particles formed by agglomeration of smaller substituents held together by localized inter-substituent bridges in the absence of compaction can be very weak indeed, as already noted in Fig. 3 for sand pellets with internal NaCl bridges. At the “strong” end of this weak agglomerate range, [Ålander *et al.* \(2004\)](#) used a platen apparatus to measure strengths of (0.2 to 6) MPa for approximately 0.5 mm polycrystalline paracetamol agglomerates formed by crystallization from solution. Presumably the substituent crystals, about 0.1 mm in size, were bound within the particles by primary bonds and the small strength reflects particle porosity. Similarly, [Knoop *et al.* \(2016\)](#) used acoustic methods to measure strengths of (0.4 to 4) MPa for (1 to 3) mm agglomerates of glass sub-particles, also about 0.1 mm in size, held together by van der Waals forces and water capillary bridges. Direct platen measurements by [Wollborn *et al.* \(2017\)](#) of similar agglomerates with slightly different glass surface preparation exhibited strengths of (0.03 to 0.17) MPa. [Adi *et al.* \(2011\)](#) also used a direct platen test to measure the strengths of spray-dried mannitol agglomerates formed into 1.5 mm particles from 3 μm substituents, with the intention of assessing aerosol use. Strengths of (0.003 to 0.183) MPa were observed and correlated with agglomerate vapor dispersion. [Das *et al.* \(2013\)](#) were similarly concerned and inferred strengths of (0.001 to 0.1) MPa from agglomerate size measurements of (18 to 24) μm lactose substituents for aerosol use. At the weakest end of the agglomerate strength range, [Mueller *et al.* \(2017\)](#) formed 3 mm, approximately 1.4 mg, particles from (40 to 90) μm volcanic ash or glass substituents, deliberately bound with NaCl bridges, in order to mimic and model volcanic plume activity. Particle impact measurements showed increased fragmentation energy required for particles containing greater

amounts of NaCl and inferred particle strengths of approximately (0.01 to 0.03) MPa. Extensive strength edf $Pr(\sigma)$ data in unbiased form were presented in the studies of the stronger agglomerate particles by [Ålander *et al.*](#), [Knoop *et al.*](#), and [Wollborn *et al.*](#) In the first case, the data are identical to the characteristic concave particle strength distributions of Fig. 6, reflecting heavy tail flaw populations. In the next two cases the data are very similar to the strength distributions of the small alumina particles in Fig. 16—almost linear variations at small strengths perturbed by curvature at large strengths and weak variation of the threshold, indicative of dominant stochastic and weak deterministic effects on strength. As above with tablets, the strengths of porous agglomerate particles are consistent with other particle measurements.

Two other phenomena may affect the behavior of particles. The first occurs if reactive species can gain access to a tensile region of the particle during loading. This is particularly important for the pervasive case of inorganic oxide or related particles, in which water or moisture is extremely surface reactive leading to stress-corrosion cracking. Such cracking generates loading rate effects in brittle material strength tests as the kinetics of crack-tip bond reactions affect crack propagation velocities and thence fracture stability. At slow loading rates, the strength is invariant, reflecting near complete reaction, for water, hydrolysis, of the cracked surface. As the rate increases the strength increases, reflecting incomplete reaction and greater surface energy. The phenomena are discussed in detail elsewhere ([Lawn, 1993](#); [Cook, 2015](#)), with the essential point that inorganic particle strength should increase with increasing loading rate. Such effects have been observed ([Yashima, 1989](#), as reported by [Ryu and Saito, 1991](#)) for borosilicate glass, quartz, and limestone particles, in which the strength doubled as the loading rate was increased by about 10^7 , consistent with other brittle material oxide observations ([Cook, 2015](#)). In the work of [Yashima](#), the particle materials were dense and crack propagation effects were likely restricted to particle surfaces. If the particles contained open porosity, *e.g.*, the bauxites of [Bertrand *et al.* \(1988\)](#), moisture assisted crack propagation effects could affect the tensile central volume of the particle.

The second phenomenon is also dependent on the details of any porosity and affects the behavior of extremely compliant particles. [Lin *et al.* \(2008\)](#) examined the compression behavior of large, multi-centimeter, sponge and rubber spheres and demonstrated significant differences between compressible (porous sponge) and incompressible (dense rubber) materials. [Lin *et al.*](#) also noted the effects of water motion in the porous structure, which would lead to poroelastic effects,

and the likely convolution with viscoelastic effects, leading to simultaneous time-dependent behavior as noted by [Strange *et al.* \(2013\)](#) in porous gels.

X. CONCLUSIONS

The strength distributions of small particles are distinctly different from those of large specimens. Particle strength distributions are broad and concave, predominantly exhibiting perturbed linear behavior, compared with narrow, sigmoidal behavior of large specimens. Particle strength distributions are determined by localization of a tensile zone to the center of a diametrically-loaded particle such that particle failure occurs from a fixed location independent of flaw size, thereby moderating extreme value effects in failure. Conversely, large specimen failure is determined by extreme value effects, in which failure occurs at the largest, extreme, flaw, independent of location. As a consequence of this difference, particle strength distributions often avoid extreme value size effects and reflect the complete underlying strength-controlling flaw population. The majority of flaw populations in particles are shown to have a heavy tail at large crack lengths, such that failure at large flaws with small strengths is more frequent than observed with large specimens. Size effects in particle failure are divided between a majority of systems exhibiting deterministic size effects, in which particle size determines the flaw population, and a minority of systems exhibiting stochastic size effects, in which the population is invariant and particle size determines the probability of independent flaw selection. Deterministic systems are distinguished by the commonly observed variation in threshold strength with particle size, whereas stochastic systems are distinguished by the less common invariant threshold. These conclusions extend across all particle sizes, from sub-micrometer to multi-centimeter, and across all particle materials, including sand, rocks, cement, abrasives, and food. Broadly, the median strengths of dense particles decrease as $(\text{particle size})^{-1/2}$, implying a simple scaling of median flaw size with particle size; agglomerates are weaker than dense particles. Future work would benefit greatly from presentation of particle strength distributions in unbiased formats, such that size scaling (extreme value, deterministic, stochastic) and material behavior (*e.g.*, heavy tail flaw distributions) can be assessed easily. In detail, future work should focus on development of models and descriptions of deterministic size effects (stochastic effects are well described), on measurements

of strength distributions of tablets and porous materials, and on rate effects in particle failure influenced by stress-corrosion cracking and poroelastic and viscoelastic deformation.

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